

**The Role of Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks
In Empowering Sri Lankan Entrepreneurs in Hungary**

Author:

Rajapaksha Mudiyanseelage Chamila Prabhodhani Bandara

Budapest Metropolitan University

MSc.in Management and Leadership

Thesis Advisor:

Prof. Eszter Marcellné Szilágyi

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the role of entrepreneurial leadership and community networking in empowering Sri Lankan entrepreneurs residing in Hungary. Motivated by both my academic background in management and leadership and personal entrepreneurial aspirations as a foreign resident, this research focuses on a small yet well-educated Sri Lankan community with entrepreneurial ambitions in Hungary. As Sri Lankans increasingly migrate to Hungary for educational and professional opportunities, understanding the factors that facilitate their entrepreneurial success is vital. Despite this, little prior research has explored how leadership skills and community networks impact their business outcomes. To address this gap, a mixed-methods approach was employed. Quantitative data were gathered from 98 Sri Lankan respondents via an online questionnaire, while qualitative insights were obtained through semi-structured interviews with five aspiring Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary. The study aimed to evaluate how entrepreneurial leadership and community support influence motivation and empowerment among these potential entrepreneurs. Findings indicate that robust community networks and strong leadership capabilities significantly enhance entrepreneurial aspirations and success within this group. This research contributes to the broader understanding of how diaspora communities leverage leadership and networking to establish businesses abroad. The results also offer valuable implications for policymakers and support organizations seeking to foster immigrant entrepreneurship in Hungary.

Keywords: *entrepreneurial leadership, community network, entrepreneurial empowerment, Sri Lankan community in Hungary*

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- BTI Project** - Bertelsmann Transformation Index Project
- CAP** - Common Agricultural Policy
- CIA** - Central Intelligence Agency
- EU** - European Union
- Fidesz** - Alliance of Young Democrats (Fiatal Demokraták Szövetsége)
- GDP** - Gross Domestic Product
- IMF** - International Monetary Fund
- KDNP** - Christian Democratic People's Party (Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt in Hungarian)
- KESMA** - Central European Press and Media Foundation (Közép-Európai Sajtó és Média Alapítvány in Hungarian)
- KM** - Knowledge Management
- LGBTQ+** - Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer/Questioning, and others
- MA** - Master of Arts
- MSc** - Master of Science
- NGO** - Non-Governmental Organization
- OECD** - Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
- PLOS** - Public Library of Science
- SME** - Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
- UNDP** - United Nations Development Programme
- UNESCO** - United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

CHAPTER 1 : RESEARCH BACKGROUND

1.1 Introduction

The topic of my study is “The Role of Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks in Empowering Sri Lankan Entrepreneurs in Hungary.” An entrepreneur not only focuses on personal growth but also contributes to economic development, social progress, innovation, and job creation, thereby stimulating the economy (Carree & Thurik, 2010). At present, the concept of entrepreneurship extends beyond national borders, allowing individuals to build their economic stability without being restricted by national boundaries. As migrant entrepreneurs, they can contribute to the host country’s economy while simultaneously developing their financial stability, enhancing creative skills, and demonstrating resilience (Schäfer & Henn, 2018; Solano et al., 2022; Wurth et al., 2022). Generally, becoming a migrant entrepreneur requires immense determination, and they often encounter challenges such as language barriers, legal restrictions, and cultural differences when striving for success or establishing stability (Guerrero et al., 2021; Neumeyer et al., 2019).

My study focuses on the essential role of entrepreneurial leadership and community networks in overcoming these challenges. Specifically, it aims to examine how Sri Lankans who migrate to Hungary are empowered as entrepreneurs through leadership and networking. Furthermore, a significant number of Sri Lankans migrating to Hungary aspire to become entrepreneurs. As a foreign community, their interaction with Hungarian nationals, who speak a unique language, raises curiosity about how they develop businesses and integrate into the local market. Kostova & Radaev (2010) state that for migrants to positively impact entrepreneurial activities, they must integrate with the networks of the host country. Similarly, Guerrero et al. (2021) reveal that many Sri Lankans and other migrants arriving in Hungary for educational and professional aspirations face challenges related to language, legal regulations, and cultural barriers.

As a Sri Lankan migrant in Hungary striving to establish myself as an entrepreneur, one of my study goals is to provide insights and support for fellow Sri Lankan entrepreneurs pursuing similar paths. The key motivation behind my research stems from my academic background and the existing research gap. Since 1956, Sri Lankans have been migrating to Hungary for various professional and educational reasons, and a considerable number continue to do so each year (Sri Lankan Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2021). Studies indicate that migrant entrepreneurship significantly contributes to economic growth and job creation worldwide

(Kerr & Kerr, 2020). However, there has been no prior research on Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary, their ambitions, or the challenges they face in establishing businesses. Recognizing this research gap, my study aims to explore the entrepreneurial landscape of Sri Lankan migrants in Hungary, focusing on their business aspirations, challenges, and success factors. I adopted a mixed-methods research approach, incorporating both primary and secondary data collection methods. Mixed-methods research enables a comprehensive understanding of the research problem by integrating qualitative and quantitative data (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Accordingly, this study examines the role of entrepreneurial leadership and community networks in empowering Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary using a combined methodological approach. A literature review was conducted using online academic databases such as Google Scholar to identify research gaps and develop a theoretical framework (Boote & Beile, 2005). The review included academic articles, research papers, and relevant literature on entrepreneurial leadership, migrant entrepreneurship, and community networks.

For primary data collection, two research methods were used. Semi-structured interviews and A structured questionnaire. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with five participants to explore their entrepreneurial experiences, skills, community connections, and challenges. A structured questionnaire was distributed via Google Forms to 98 Sri Lankans living in Hungary to gather quantitative data on entrepreneurial aspirations, leadership skills, networking, business challenges, and economic conditions. This study explores five key research questions as “What are the key leadership qualities that contribute to the success of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary?” and “How do community networks influence the entrepreneurial empowerment of Sri Lankan business owners in Hungary?”, “What role does business knowledge and skill development play in entrepreneurial success?”, “What challenges do Sri Lankan entrepreneurs face in Hungary, and how do they overcome them?”, and “How can entrepreneurial leadership and community support structures be optimized to enhance business sustainability?”

This study is organized into seven chapters. Chapter 1 provides an overview of the study, including the research background. Chapter 2 reviews existing literature on entrepreneurial empowerment. Chapter 3 explains the research methodology, and Chapters 4,5, and 6 analysed the collected data and findings. Chapter 7 presents the conclusions and recommendations. Thus, this study was systematically conducted and documented to investigate “The Role of

Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks in Empowering Sri Lankan Entrepreneurs in Hungary.”

1.2 Business and social environment in Sri Lanka and Hungary

I am going to review some basic data, the most important knowledge of the social and cultural background, and some main characteristics of the political and economic situation of the two countries in my research: Sri Lanka and Hungary. This review has the further purpose of offering a good background of information, both for the comparative analysis of the 2 countries and also to understand the environmental analysis of the possible entrepreneurial activities in my primary research.

1.2.1 Introduction of Sri Lanka

Sri Lanka is a beautiful island country and it is located in South Asia. It is officially introduced as “Democratic Socialist Republic of Sri Lanka”. It is located in the Indian Ocean and southeast of India. The strategic location of Sri Lanka has made it possible to establish numerous foreign invasions and foreign trade relations since ancient times. Accordingly, many Portuguese, Dutch, and British colonial rule influences have been exerted on Sri Lanka (Senaratne, 2018). In addition, its geographical location has facilitated economic and diplomatic relations with major global business powers such as China and India under the concept of "One Belt and One Road" (Vignarajah, 2020). Sri Lanka is located between 5°55'6°9' north latitude and 79°41–81°53' east longitude and has a land area of approximately 65,610 square kilometers (Central Intelligence Agency [CIA], 2021). This unique geographical location has made Sri Lanka a significant maritime hub since ancient times. Sri Lanka is also in high demand for strategic geopolitical purposes.

Sri Lanka's climate is predominantly tropical, and it is constantly influenced by the Indian Ocean and the Bay of Bengal. Sri Lanka is divided into three primary climatic zones under climate change. They are the Wet Zone, the Dry Zone, and the Intermediate Zone (Domroes & Ranatunge, 1993). The rain varies across the climate zones. The Wet Zone is located mainly in the southwestern region, and due to the southwest monsoon, it receives rainfall (May to September) throughout the year. But the Dry Zone, covering most of the northern and eastern parts of Sri Lanka, has a more arid climate. Due to this arid, it gets seasonal rainfall during the northeast monsoon from December to February, but the Intermediate Zone, situated between

these two zones, has mixed climatic characteristics whole the year (Domroes & Ranatunge, 1993). Sri Lanka is administratively divided into nine provinces they are the Western, Central, Southern, Northern, Eastern, North Western, North Central, Uva, and Sabaragamuwa. These nine provinces have been subdivided into twenty-five districts, each with its own distinct climatic, socioeconomic, and geographic characteristics. (Department of Census and Statistics [DCS], 2021). The Western Province, which includes Colombo, the commercial capital, is the most urbanized and densely populated region, whereas the Northern and Eastern Provinces are noted for their cultural and ethnic diversity, with significant Tamil and Muslim populations. The Western Province, which includes the Colombo District as the commercial capital, has become a more urbanized and densely populated region. (Department of Census and Statistics [DCS], 2021).

The strategic location of Sri Lanka has made it a maritime trade hub between the Middle East and Asia. The Abundant natural resources and rich cultural history have made Sri Lanka a unique and important country in South Asia. Sri Lanka is a unique creation of nature, and it is a beautiful island nation in South Asia that offers unparalleled hospitality. Despite facing economic and political challenges such as foreign debt and political instability, ambitious plans are being formulated to advance development. Improving infrastructure, managing sustainable resources, and working to enhance global trade relations are notable features of the plans. Sri Lankan spices and coconuts are very popular worldwide, and Sri Lankan cuisine maintains its cultural identity. Moreover, Sri Lanka is a country with centuries-old artistic traditions that have earned it a shining international reputation for its batik textiles, wood carvings, traditional masks, handicrafts, and ivory crafts (Rodrigo, 2020). Considering the geographical and climatic features of Sri Lanka, it covers an area of approximately 65,610 square km., and is characterized by a variety of topographies, including coastal plains, central mountains, dense forests, and a wide range of climatic variations (Weerasinghe, 2020). Thus, seasonal changes naturally support agricultural patterns and water availability (Fernando et al., 2019).

Piduruthalagala Mountain (2,524 m) is the highest peak in the country, and the central highlands play an important role in regulating the climate and water resources of the island (Gunathilaka and Wijesundara, 2019). Sri Lanka has a tropical climate with two main monsoon seasons, due to the current adverse environmental impacts, climate changes are increasing, causing severe weather conditions such as prolonged droughts and severe floods, but the government is implementing strategies for this (Jayasundara et al., 2021). Sri Lanka has had

the best hydrological network since ancient times. The Mahaweli River is the longest in Sri Lanka, spanning over 335 km, and is dominated by numerous rivers and streams. The Mahaweli River originates from the central highland and flows into the Bay of Bengal at Trincomalee. This irrigation system plays a crucial role in agriculture and hydroelectric power generation (Irrigation Department of Sri Lanka, 2020). Other Sri Lankan rivers (Kelani, Kalu, and Walawe Rivers) contribute to agricultural productivity. (Irrigation Department of Sri Lanka, 2020)

In terms of natural resources and economy, Sri Lanka is endowed with fertile lands, minerals, and marine resources. It contributes significantly to the economy through these resources and tea, rubber, and coconut plantations (Bandara, 2021). The fisheries industry is an important industrial sector in the Sri Lankan economy, with the production of marine resources for both domestic consumption and export. The production and export of garments are providing significant benefits to the Sri Lankan economy. According to this cultural and natural beauty, tourism plays an important role in the Sri Lankan economy. (Samaranayake, 2022). Sri Lanka has eight UNESCO-designated World Heritage Sites, including Anuradhapura, Polonnaruwa, the Sigiriya rock fortress, and the sacred city of Kandy. The tourism industry of Sri Lanka was devastated by the COVID-19 pandemic but is also recovering (Fernando, 2021).

1.2.2 Religion, culture, language, and typical educational and lifestyle Patterns in Sri Lanka.

Religion is given great importance in Sri Lankan society. Religion and culture combine to represent the Sri Lankan identity. Sri Lankan culture plays a significant role and has influenced social values, festivals, and daily practices since ancient times. Sri Lanka is a peaceful country with no civil wars, comprising various ethnic groups including Sinhalese, Tamils, and Burghers (Department of Census and Statistics, Sri Lanka, 2024). Sinhala and Tamil are the official languages of Sri Lanka, and English is also widely spoken (Gamage, 2020). Buddhism is the main religion of Sri Lanka with a historical and cultural heritage spanning over 2,500 years. Buddhism religion is about 70% of the population in Sri Lanka, and the majority is Sinhalese. (De Silva, 2019) Hinduism is followed mainly by the Tamil population, and Tamils live in large numbers, especially in the Northern and Eastern provinces. The Islamic religion is followed by the Muslim community, and currently, the Muslim population is overwhelmingly high. Christianity, introduced during the colonial period, is practiced not only by the Burghers but also by the Sinhalese and Tamil communities to a significant extent. (Pieris, 2021).

Buddhists are living in harmony with Hindus, Catholics, and Muslims also. It has approximately 22 million of population, with the Sinhalese being the majority ethnic group. Sri Lanka is a multilingual nation, with Sinhala and Tamil as its official languages, but English literacy is also high. English is used as a lingua franca, especially in business, education, and government processes (Fernando, 2018). Sinhala is mainly used by Sinhala Buddhists and the Catholic community, while Tamil language is used by the Tamil and Muslim communities. The government has identified language policies intending to promote social harmony to prevent the recurrence of such conflicts, drawing lessons from the ethnic conflicts that occurred ten years ago (Rambukwella, 2020).

Sri Lanka has a rich artistic heritage that includes traditional dance, music, and architecture. There are many classical dance forms in the Upcountry, Lowcountry, and Sabaragamuwa regions, and these dances are performed during state and religious ceremonies. (Gamage, 2020). Traditional music also plays a central role in Sri Lankan culture. There are many musical instruments, mainly drums. Sri Lankan art is known worldwide for its paintings and colors found in ancient cave paintings such as those at Sigiriya (Gamage, 2020). Sri Lanka is a multicultural society. Each culture has its unique festivals, which are celebrated peacefully during different months of the year. The Sinhala and Tamil New Year is celebrated in April, and it symbolizes the unity of the Sinhala and Tamil communities. Vesak festival, which commemorates the birth, enlightenment, and death of the Buddha, also falls in May (De Silva, 2019). Diwali is celebrated by Hindus, Eid-ul-Fitr and Eid-ul-Adha are celebrated by Muslims, and Christmas is also celebrated by the Christian community.

Sri Lanka is known as a country with free education, as primary, secondary, and tertiary education is provided free of charge through schools, and it has the highest literacy rates in South Asia. (Ministry of Education, Sri Lanka, 2022). The Sri Lankan education system is a 13-year system, consisting of primary education from grades 1 to 5, junior-secondary from grades 6 to 9, senior-secondary from grades 9 to 11, and university level from grades 12 to 13 (World Bank, 2021). Students who qualify for university admission are also provided with 4 years of free university education. Sri Lankan students must continue their education until the age of 13. (Perera, 2020). Vocational training with specialized skills relevant to the labor market is expected from education, while educational propaganda has also made technology building and bilingual education mandatory. Accordingly, Sri Lankans with quality education

are prepared to perform at any level of profession in the world (Ministry of Education, Sri Lanka, 2022).

The lifestyle of Sri Lankans appears to be very peaceful and slowly evolving. Due to geographical, cultural, and economic factors, a mixture of traditional and modern influences exists in the lifestyle (Fernando, 2019). While urban and rural areas exhibit different lifestyles, cities such as Colombo, Galle, and Kandy have urban lifestyles. Urban populations, accustomed to a faster-paced lifestyle, make extensive use of modern amenities and technology, which also gives them greater access to global cultural influences (Wijesinghe, 2021). In rural areas, agricultural practices are prevalent, especially rice and dairy farming, and daily activities are more harmonious and peaceful than in urban areas (Fernando, 2019). In Sri Lanka, the family factor has been given more space. Family structures have become increasingly widespread, with multiple generations living together, with strong family ties and collective responsibilities. Traditional gender roles are gradually changing today, and women in urban society are also relatively active in professional sectors (Perera, 2020). Eating a heavy meal of rice and curry is a Sri Lankan habit. While coastal communities consume more seafood, people in the central highlands consume fresh vegetables and spices. Leisure activities include playing sports and going on excursions that are indigenous to Sri Lanka (De Silva, 2019).

1.2.3 History review and current political/social structures in Sri Lanka.

The history of Sri Lanka has evolved to its current state of development. It has been complex and multifaceted, and it has experienced periods of political stability, cultural prosperity, and significant social upheaval. The recorded history of Sri Lanka begins in the 6th century BC. Accordingly, the first kingdom of Sri Lanka was Anuradhapura. It was the beginning of seven other kingdoms. According to archaeological evidence, there was advanced urban planning and agriculture even before foreign invaders conquered Sri Lanka. According to the *Mahavanshaya*, an ancient historical chronicle, King Vijaya is said to have been the founder of Sri Lankan civilization (De Silva, 1981).

The longest-lasting ancient monarchy in South Asia was the Anuradhapura Kingdom. Wickramasinghe (2006). King Devanampiya Tissa embraced Buddhism in the 3rd. century BC, an event that had a significant positive impact on the cultural and religious landscape of the entire country (Wickramasinghe, 2006). Irrigation systems and monasteries demonstrate the advanced infrastructure of the state at that time, as well as the technical prowess,

architectural design, and organizational skills of the state and its citizens (Gunawardena, 2001). After the decline of the Anuradhapura Kingdom, the Polonnaruwa Kingdom emerged in 1017 – 1236 AD, and the legacy of cultural and political development was also maintained by that kingdom (Perera, 1992). King Parakramabahu (1153–1186), who ruled during this period, rendered invaluable service to agriculture. The reservoirs and canals created during that time are still used for agriculture today (Perera, 1992).

The arrival of European colonial powers, after the rule of eight kingdoms, marked a significant turning point in the history of Sri Lanka (Mendis, 1993). The Portuguese, Dutch, and British all did a good job in shaping the political and economic structures of the island, but it also led to the destruction of Sri Lankan culture (Brown, 2015). The Portuguese conquered Sri Lanka from 1505–1658, establishing settlements on the island and exerting influence in the coastal areas for nearly a century and a half. The Portuguese introduced Catholicism to Sri Lanka and began the spice trade and exportation. The export of Sri Lankan natural resources brought them into conflict with the native Sinhala kings (Mendis, 1993). In 1658, they kept control of the cinnamon and many plantation crops of Sri Lanka, which had been conquered by the Dutch. However, their rule was short-lived, and the British took control of the island in 1796 after defeating the Dutch. The British exploited the plantation economy, tea, rubber, and coffee cultivation, but they introduced a good transport system and infrastructure until Sri Lanka gained independence in 1948. The tea crop they introduced remains Sri Lanka's main export plantation crop today (Brown, 2015).

The independence struggle in Sri Lanka began to free itself from foreign occupation, and the early 20th century saw the rise of nationalist movements. Accordingly, the formation of the Ceylon National Congress in 1919 marked the beginning of organized political movements for independence (Kiernan, 2002). In 1948, the first Prime Minister of Sri Lanka, which gained independence from British colonial rule, was Don Stephen Senanayake, and Sri Lanka became a republic after gaining independence from the British Dominion in 1972 (Rajasingham, 2004). After the independence of Sri Lanka, social and political problems arose, with ethnic conflicts between the Sinhalese majority and the Tamil minority. A brutal civil war broke out in 1983, but by 2009 the entire island had become a peaceful state, ending the war. However, the war resulted in significant loss of life, leaving permanent scars on the social fabric of the country (Rajasingham, 2004). It focused on rebuilding the country's economy and infrastructure, but political instability is currently challenging the nation's development (Jayaratne, 2012).

According to the 1978 Constitution of Sri Lanka, the President serves for five years. He is responsible for overseeing national security, appointing ministers, and making decisions on foreign policy. The Prime Minister presides over the Parliament and is the head of the Cabinet (Peiris, 2017). The separation and independence of the judiciary from the legislature and executive are also special features of the Sri Lankan state (Constitution of Sri Lanka, 1978). The centralization of the broad powers of the executive presidency by a few current presidents led to the emergence of authoritarian rule and the collapse of the country's economy. However, the socialist governance system that has emerged today is rebuilding the collapsed political and economic society (Jayasuriya, 2018).

The social structure of Sri Lanka reflects its ethnic diversity and cultural forces. The Population of the country is composed of three major ethnic groups. They are Sinhalese (75%), Tamils (15%), and Muslims (9%) (Schalk, 2016). The state religion, Theravada of Sri Lanka, is Buddhism it plays an essential role in shaping Sri Lanka's national identity. Buddhism (Buddhist monks) has positively influenced political decisions and policies on Sinhalese nationalism and ethnic unity. (Schalk, 2016). Primarily Tamil community is practicing Hinduism, and temples, festivals, and traditional practices are deeply rooted in Tamil culture (Rajasuriya, 2014). Christianity was introduced during colonial times, and significant presence, particularly among the Sinhala and Tamil populations in urban centers. The Muslim community influences local economies, especially in the Eastern provinces, where Muslims maintain strong social and business networks. (Peiris, 2017). These social and political changes and struggles that have been unfolding over the past have had a significant impact on the positive development of Sri Lankan society, and have also created a collapse of the Sri Lankan economy, a decline in entrepreneurship, and a widespread brain drain in the present (Gunsekera, 2023).

1.2.4 Current economic/ social/ political challenges in Sri Lanka

Current social, economic, and political challenges of Sri Lanka are deeply intertwined and they are hindering future development in the country. Nowadays Sri Lanka is struggling to recover from a devastating economic crisis, which has heightened unemployment, inflation, and poverty. In the meantime, ethnic and religious divisions continue to fuel social unrest and political instability. Years of political corruption, lack of institutional reforms, and the exchange of power between families have prevented all Sri Lankans from being able to create a more stable and prosperous future.

The main reason for the current economic crisis in Sri Lanka is poor financial management. Financial crises have arisen due to factors such as the accumulation of external debt and the failure of debt and economic policies (Weerakoon, 2023). There is a borrowing capacity that should be obtained by a country. However, due to borrowing beyond the limit, Sri Lanka is currently suffering from debt. Recent political decisions show that external borrowing, particularly from international sovereign bonds and bilateral lenders such as China, has been ongoing for some time, and that reliance on such debt has created unsustainable debt levels (Fernando and Karunaratne, 2022). Studies conducted by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) (2023) have confirmed that Sri Lanka's politically motivated tax cuts in 2019 have significantly reduced government revenue, leading to a gradual increase in fiscal deficits. The COVID-19 pandemic spread across Sri Lanka in 2019, accelerating the economic downturn as it reduced foreign exchange inflows from tourism and remittances (Wickramasinghe, 2023).

Another significant political policy was the sudden shift from chemical farming to organic farming, launching failed agricultural programs in 2019. As a result, all long-standing agricultural policies were halted, and yields in Sri Lanka's main export crops and paddy farming declined. This led to food shortages and increased imports, while the collapse in production led to a decline in per capita income and an increase in the cost of living (Jayasundara, 2022). During this period, a foreign exchange crisis emerged as the ability to import essential goods in Sri Lanka was severely restricted, leading to inflationary pressures and currency devaluation (Amarasekara 2023). Whatever economic problems arose, actions such as imposing import restrictions and obtaining financial assistance from international organizations appear to have deepened the economic crisis rather than being proactive in response (ADB, 2024).

The economic crisis in Sri Lanka has also deepened the social consequences, creating social protests, declining living standards, and rising poverty rates (Perera, 2023). World Bank (2023) reports show that current Sri Lankan inflation has led to increased food insecurity, a collapse in essential services such as healthcare and education, and a widening funding gap. This is why many Sri Lankans are leaving the country. These reports reveal that there is currently a brain drain and that social corruption and illegal social activities are also taking place, leading to social decline. Empirical studies conducted by Gunasekara and de Silva (2024) on child malnutrition rates and rural development reveal that child malnutrition has increased in Sri Lanka and that social equity has been broken down among rural communities.

Severe inequalities have been created between the capitalist and the proletariat, and the emergence of class and cast conflicts due to social inequalities is severely detrimental to the current and future social development of the country. Social tensions were the cause of the protests, which were sparked by public frustration over government mismanagement, corruption, and the rising cost of living. As a result, Mr. Gotabaya Rajapaksa's resignation in 2023 will go down in history as the first president in Sri Lankan history to be ousted after a popular uprising. The "Aragalaya" movement demonstrated the power of citizen action in shaping political outcomes, and it was during this period that the people gained the strength to stand up against social injustice (Fernando, 2023). The political crises of Sri Lanka are often deeply intertwined with its economic and social challenges (Hettige, 2023). The misuse of the privileges of the executive presidency, created after 1978, to exert social pressure and to centralize wealth and power only among relatives, demonstrates the corruption of Sri Lankan politics (Hettige, 2023). Regrettably, the Rajapaksa family's administration has been able to bring a great country to economic and social decline since 2005.

The literature suggests that the failure to heed the warnings of economic experts since 2019, led to widespread public opposition, ultimately leading to a change in the regime (Kalegama, 2023). This period was marked by political instability in the country, due to corruption and the undermining of the rule of law. Foreign aid and loans were needed to help Sri Lanka recover, but political resistance has hindered implementation (IMF, 2024). The IMF, in 2023, instructed Sri Lanka to carry out structural reforms, including reducing government spending and improving transparency, but these were not properly implemented by the government. It is believed that the economy of Sri Lanka, stability, and the collapsed social situation can be restored under Mr. Anura Kumara Dissanayake, a socialist president who came to power with great popular support in 2025 (Samarasinghe, 2024).

1.3 Typical resources, whether inhabitants of Hungary

Hungary is a landlocked country in Central Europe and is known for its rich history, diverse geography, and significant cultural contributions. Hungary is situated in the "*Carpathian Basin*" and it is bordered by Austria, Slovakia, Ukraine, Romania, Serbia, Croatia, and Slovenia (Pinter, 2020). The total area of Hungary is approximately 93,030 square kilometers (Central Intelligence Agency [CIA], 2021). The country has a predominantly Hungarian ethnic composition. Minority groups such as Roma, Germans, and Slovaks live in the country, contributing to its cultural diversity, and the country has a multi-religious character due to

various immigrants. The official language is Hungarian, which is part of the Finno-Ugric language family (Koksis and Hodósi, 2020).

The topography of Hungary is plain. It is landlocked and devoid of large mountain ranges or Abyss, and it is mainly characterized by plains. The Great Hungarian Plain (Alföld) covers a significant part of the territory, and tributary rivers such as the Danube and Tisza flow through the country, playing a major role in the agriculture of Hungary and the transportation of export and import goods (Molnar, 2019). The climate of Hungary is characterized by hot summers, cold winters, and moderate temperatures (Pongrácz et al., 2013). Winter temperatures can drop below freezing, with January being the coldest month. During the summer season, especially in July and August, the average maximum temperature is around 25–30°C (77–86°F), and weather reports indicate that heat waves can cause temperatures to rise even higher. Moreover, spring and autumn are transitional periods with mild temperatures and moderate rainfall. (Bartholy & Pongrácz, 2007). Annual precipitation varies widely across Hungary due to precipitation and extreme weather events.

The western and northern regions receive more rainfall than the eastern plains, with average annual rainfall varying from 500 mm in the lowlands to 800 mm in the mountainous areas (Lakatos et al., 2011). Climate models show that warming trends in Hungary will lead to changes in precipitation patterns due to rising temperatures, affecting agriculture and water resources, and causing more frequent droughts (Bartholy et al., 2009). In addition, public safety will be at risk as more intense storms and flood events will occur (Jolánkai, 2011).

Hungary places significant emphasis on the economy, agriculture, and energy production such as including bauxite, coal, and natural gas, and it relies heavily on natural resources, including land, fossil fuels, minerals, and water resources (European Commission, 2021). The amount of land available for agriculture in Hungary is approximately 59% of the total area of the country (European Environment Agency, 2015). Accordingly, crops such as wheat, corn, sunflower seeds, maize, and barley are successfully grown in this fertile plain, but environmental challenges such as soil erosion and acidification threaten long-term agricultural sustainability (World Bank, 2020). Industries including automotive manufacturing, pharmaceuticals, and information technology also appear to play an important role in contributing to the economy (OECD, 2021). Regarding sustainability and resource management, Hungary outlines strategies for rural development, implementing the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and strategic plans (European Commission, 2021).

Hungary is a country rich in traditions, cultural heritage, and tourism opportunities, with a long history and customs as well as natural attractions. It has a deep-rooted cultural heritage, with traditional customs and festivals. Folk music, dance, and artistic creations such as embroidery and handicrafts are key elements of Hungarian culture (Bartók, 2018). One of the most famous traditions in Hungary is the Busójárás festival in Mohács, where locals wear wooden masks and sheepskin coats to celebrate the end of winter (UNESCO, 2021). Moreover, the Budapest Wine Festival, which highlights centuries-old winemaking traditions, is also famous among the celebrations of Saint Stephen's Day on August 20, which marks the foundation of the Hungarian state (Hungarian Tourism Agency, 2020). Ecotourism and rural tourism are important in Hungary. In addition to the well-known urban tourist centers, the famous Aggtelek National Park, home to the famous Baradla Cave, attracts nature enthusiasts and speleologists (European Environment Agency, 2020). Tourism is experiencing high growth as the pandemic progresses, playing a crucial role in the economy, contributing approximately 10% to GDP (World Travel and Tourism Council, 2021). The hospitality and service industries benefit significantly, but the challenges of Budapest's competitive tourism industry require sustainable management strategies (OECD, 2022).

Hungary has made more innovations and made significant contributions to global innovation in various fields. Medicine, engineering, and technology sectors are major, and the country has produced several Nobel Prize-winning scientists, such as Albert Szent-Györgyi, who discovered Vitamin C (Puskás, 2019). Hungary is also known for its advancements in information technology, renewable energy, automotive engineering, and pharmaceuticals (European Innovation Scoreboard, 2021). However, Hungarian companies and research institutions have made progress in the country's innovations. Thus, Hungary is a beautiful paradise on the European continent, which is more famous in the world.

1.3.1 People of Hungary (Religion, culture, language, typical educational and lifestyle patterns)

Hungary, with a population of around 9.6 million, has created an identity strongly influenced by historical, religious, and linguistic factors (Hungarian Central Statistics Office, 2021). Religion has played a significant role in Hungary and is shaping the identity of Hungarians. Hungary has been a predominantly Christian country, and its nation's most widely practiced faith is Roman Catholicism the faith, followed later by Calvinism and Lutheranism (Fodor, 2019). Religious disintegration in Hungary began gradually, and secularization policies during

the communist era led to a decline in religious adherence in the 20th century. Although most Hungarians today identify as Catholic, church attendance remains relatively low (Pew Research Center, 2017).

In addition, a mix of religions has developed in Hungary today, with religious minorities including Judaism and Islam contributing to Hungary's religious diversity (Kovács, 2020). Hungary is a country with a rich cultural heritage and traditions, including culinary traditions, ethnographic research, folk traditions, and music. When considering culinary traditions, one can see how traditional Hungarian culinary practices work to preserve community identity and heritage while gradually incorporating new elements (Kovács & Vajda, 2020).

Folk Traditions and Music are the main ways to show the Hungarian traditions. The culture is rich with its distinctive Folk music traditions. Hungary's culture has a blender mix and emphasizes dance as essential to national identity (Dózsa et al., 2017). The secondary grammatical aspects of language and lexical structure make it extremely challenging for non-native speakers to learn. Accordingly, the Hungarian Language is among the top three most difficult languages in the world. (Kiss, 2021). The education system in Hungary is divided into three levels: primary, secondary, and tertiary. Compulsory education in Hungary is from the ages of six to sixteen, and students can attend either a public or private school (OECD, 2020). Budapest has several thermal baths, such as the Széchenyi and Gellert baths, it is very famous in spring, but Lake Balaton is the most famous in Summer.

Hungary's social structures reflect a wide range of lifestyles. Accordingly, when considering Hungarian lifestyles, one can also see significant differences between urban and rural settings (Varga, 2021). The country's capital, Budapest, is home to a strong focus on art, music, and tourism, with the majority of its population living there. Budapest exhibits a distinctly rural society and retains an agricultural and community-based lifestyle (Varga, 2021). Family structures have evolved, with an increase in single-parent households and late marriages becoming more common (KSH, 2020). Currently, Hungary is experiencing significant development in its transportation system and digitalization, which has had a positive impact on work-life balance and social interaction (Horvath, 2021).

Hungary has experienced significant social and economic changes in recent decades, witnessing a transition from a socialist to a market economy. However, the Hungarian government is developing policies on sustainable consumption and environmental

responsibility (Csutora & Zsóka, 2011). In addition, the Hungarian healthcare sector is also facing serious challenges when it comes to productivity. The main content of this is brain drain. This is because the production of a workforce that has been aggravated by migration is currently being created (Dózsa et al., 2017). Although Hungary is a developed country in Europe, it is currently struggling with economic and social issues similar to other developed European countries and is imposing strict laws.

1.3.2 History review and current political /social structure of Hungary

The history of Hungary is a tapestry woven from periods of cultural prosperity and resilience, sacrificing everything for victory (Molnár, 2001). Hungary has been able to rise to its modern role in Europe from the start of the Carpathian Basin, but the dynamic interplay of internal developments and external influences has driven this journey. The area now known as Hungary has been inhabited since ancient times, with various groups such as the Scythians, Celts, and Romans also having left their marks. The settlement of the Carpathian Basin by the Magyars, a Finno-Ugric people, and the beginning of the Hungarian state took place in the late 9th century. Under the leadership of Árpád, the beginning of Hungary was created and laid the foundation for the future of the Hungarian nation (Molnár, 2001).

Hungary was legally transformed into a Christian kingdom with the coronation of Saint Stephen I in 1000 AD. During Stephen's reign, Hungary was centralized and integrated into the wider European community. It was a turning point in Hungarian history. The Árpád dynasty did much to promote institutional, intellectual, and literary prosperity. This period is called a period of cultural and economic growth. The "Halotti Besed" ("Funeral Sermon"), dating to the early 1190s, is considered the first known work in the Hungarian language (Encyclopaedia Britannica, n.d). The Ottoman Empire emerged in the 16th century, and its expansion into Hungarian territories posed significant challenges. After the Battle of Mohács in 1526, the Hungarian state was divided into three parts. They are: Royal Hungary under Habsburg rule, the central region under Ottoman rule, and the semi-autonomous state of Transylvania. This tripartite division lasted until the late 17th century, when the Habsburgs reoccupied the territories, forming a unified Hungary under Habsburg rule (Encyclopaedia Britannica, n.d.).

The 18th and 19th centuries were marked by efforts to establish national identity and independence, and 1848 can be considered the year of the Hungarian Revolution. A self-determination revolution demanding independence from Habsburg rule took place, and the

Austro-Hungarian Compromise of 1867 granted Hungary considerable autonomy within the Dual Monarchy. This period saw a rapid cultural, industrial, and urban renaissance (Molnár, 2001). Hungary lost a significant portion of its territory and population after World War I and the Treaty of Trianon in 1920 and also suffered significant destruction during World War II. However, in the post-war era, Hungary, which had a socialist regime under Soviet influence, transitioned to a peaceful state committed to democracy in 1989 (Molnár, 2001). Following these historical changes, Hungary experienced significant political and economic changes from the early 1990s onwards. The most important event was Hungary's official accession to the European Union in 2004. Since then, the nation has continued to move towards modern governance, reflecting its rich historical heritage (Molnár, 2001).

Over the past decade and a half, Hungary has undergone significant political changes, while facing challenges to democracy, which have led to various challenges in implementing social policies. Since 2010, it has been led by the Fidesz-KDNP coalition, under the political leadership of Prime Minister Mr. Viktor Orbán. This period is a chapter in which significant changes in politics, the constitution, and the legislature created democratic backsliding and electoral presidency. (Associated Press, 2025). Currently, the government is trying to find answers to the challenges posed by the declining birth rate and demographics and the ongoing population crisis, through various social policies (Reuters, 2025).

Hungary is a parliamentary representative democratic republic, with the Prime Minister as head of government and the President as head of state, with a largely ceremonial role. Since 2010, the Fidesz-KDNP coalition, using its super-majority in parliament, has worked to create a new constitution and implement reforms with weak institutional checks and balances (Wikipedia, 2025). As a result of these actions, the European Union has now declared Hungary "no longer a full democracy" (Wikipedia, 2025). In recent politics, the role of Péter Magyar stands out. The positive rise of the Tisza party led by him is evident. The Tisza party, founded in 2024, has rapidly gained traction and created a powerful opposition (Reuters, 2025). Current opinion polls suggest that the Tisza party is currently set to overtake Fidesz in voter preferences, potentially creating a major shift in Hungary's political dynamics ahead of the 2026 parliamentary elections (Reuters, 2025).

Considering the current social context in Hungary, demographic decline is becoming increasingly visible. The government offers tax breaks and financial incentives for families with several children and has also introduced generous family allowances. Despite these

efforts, the expected fertility rate has not yet shown an increase. Although there was a slight increase in fertility to 1.59 children per woman in 2020, the rate has remained unchanged since then. According to calculations made in early 2024, it fell to a low of 1.36 (Financial Times, 2024). In addition, social attitudes in Hungary have also been distorted by different ideologies. Due to the philosophy of authoritarianism and foreign immigration, it is in place to create a society with low civic participation. It has created a generation of young people who dream of leaving Hungary and living in a foreign country, making social development a problem. This cultural backdrop has made it a challenge for the current government to foster a more active civil society and eradicate systemic social inequalities (BTI Project, 2024).

1.3.3 Current social/economic/political challenges in Hungary

Although Hungary, a Central European nation, has opened up to Europe through various barriers, it is currently navigating a complex landscape of political, social, and economic challenges.

Hungary is facing several challenges regarding social cohesion, human rights record, and demographic stability. These challenges have been exacerbated by political decisions, cultural dynamics, broader European trends, economic crises, and external pressures. One of the biggest social problems in Hungary is "human rights and minority discrimination". The unequal treatment of minority groups, including the LGBTQ+ community, the Roma population, and refugees, is a major problem. In recent years, the Hungarian government has significantly restricted LGBTQ+ rights, and in 2020 even banned legal gender recognition for transgender and intersex people. Minors were also prohibited from depicting content, and the European Union criticized the same laws for undermining human rights (Freedom House, 2024). The Roma community in Hungary is also being treated unequally and systematically marginalized in areas such as education, housing, and employment. Moreover, the use of schools reserved for the community has limited access to quality education. This is a serious social problem. (BTI Project, 2024). In implementing migration and asylum policies, Hungary is implementing one of the strictest migration policies in the European Union, "implementing legal frameworks that make it difficult for refugees to enter or stay in the country." This has even been criticized by international human rights organizations (Freedom House, 2024).

A review of Hungary's social challenges over the past decade has revealed that freedom of expression and media pluralism have been significantly curtailed, with independent media

outlets being suffocated by political pressure. The establishment of the Central European Media Foundation (KESMA) has led to the consolidation of media outlets under state control and the restriction of media freedom (BTI Project, 2024). Moreover, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) that focus on human rights, anti-corruption, and environmental issues have been subject to increased scrutiny and public slander, with stricter laws being imposed on them, labeling them as “foreign agents” (Freedom House, 2024). Despite subsidies for large families, the birth rate in Hungary is currently falling. The government's anti-childbirth policies have failed to significantly reduce the demographic decline (European Commission, 2025). Moreover, economic uncertainty and limited career opportunities have led to a brain drain, with many young Hungarians emigrating abroad. This migration has also exacerbated current labor shortages in sectors such as healthcare and education (IMF, 2024).

Hungary is currently facing several Economic challenges. The forecast of the European Commission reveals that "consumption will remain the main growth driver, with GDP growth projected at 1.8% in 2025 and 3.1% in 2026" (European Commission, 2025). Economic uncertainties have hurt investment levels, particularly in the automotive industry. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) warns that financial imbalances and inappropriate structural policies have weakened investor confidence and limited private investment. Lack of progress in governance reforms could also lead to a long-term suspension of funding by the European Union (IMF, 2024). Inflationary pressures also pose significant challenges, and experts believe that the Monetary Council of the National Bank of Hungary should undergo significant changes due to continued borrowing, money printing, and the collapse of the value of the local currency (Reuters, 2025).

Politically, Hungary has shown a somewhat unstable nature in recent years, indicating that Hungary has experienced significant political shifts. For these reasons, a democratic backsliding has already been created as a state. That is why the European Union has declared, "Hungary is no longer a full democracy" (Wikipedia, 2025). Under strict and long-term rules of Prime Minister Viktor Orbán, the ruling Fidesz party has been accused of corruption, undermining democratic institutions, limiting judicial independence, and suppressing media freedom. Critics of this style of government have characterized Hungary as an "electoral dictatorship," where the government is tightly controlled, serving the interests of the ruling party, even under democratic processes (Associated Press, 2025).

Concerns about the political instability caused by Fidesz have led to the rise of the Tisza party, led by Péter Magyar. Tisza was founded in 2024 to dismantle the existing "national solidarity system" established by Fidesz. The Tisza party is currently notable for its compliance with the transparency, anti-corruption measures, and democratic norms expected by the European Union (Wikipedia, 2025). A look at recent political instability reveals that there are several weaknesses and vulnerabilities in current politics, such as authoritarianism, direct and quick decisions, unstable orders/economic policies made on the spur of the moment, the use of politics as a family organization, and long-term control. Therefore, recent polls suggest that the Tisza party has gained significant traction and could pose a significant challenge to the long-term dominance of the Fidesz party in the future (Reuters, 2025). As mentioned above, Hungary is currently facing a set of severe social, economic, and political challenges.

1.4 Connections between Sri Lanka and Hungary

1.4.1 connections of international trade

The bilateral relations between Hungary and Sri Lanka have steadily developed in recent years. These relations can be categorized into several areas, with significant focus on innovation, trade, and governmental technical cooperation. As a result, Hungary currently exports machinery, chemicals, and vehicles to Sri Lanka, while Sri Lanka exports tea, spices, and agricultural products to Hungary (Rath & Swagerman, 2016). Due to the existing bilateral relations, the ongoing investments focus not only on manufacturing, construction, and high-tech sectors but also on agricultural industries (Rath & Swagerman, 2016). According to current reports and information, economically, trade between the two countries remains moderate. However, Hungary has provided significant support for Sri Lanka's infrastructure development. Accordingly, financial contributions have been made for several water management and renewable energy projects (Hungarian Export Promotion Agency, 2020).

Although both countries are not widely open to global trade and maintain a relatively limited trade volume, the mutual relationship established between Sri Lanka and Hungary has a strong positive impact on education, infrastructure, and sustainable development.

1.4.2 Diplomatic ties between the two nations

When expecting a country's progress on a global scale, it is essential to establish international collaborations. Without such cooperation, a nation cannot anticipate stability or development within the business and international spheres. Currently, Hungary and Sri Lanka maintain

strong diplomatic relations through continuous engagement with global organizations such as the United Nations. These diplomatic ties form the foundation for economic, social, and cultural advancement. To enhance people-to-people connections and achieve developmental goals, greater emphasis should be placed on cultural diplomacy (Welter, 2011). With the integration of sectors like tourism, information technology, and education, business opportunities expand. Strengthening these collaborations facilitates international trade operations, fostering business networking (Creswell & Plano-Clark, 2018).

At present, Sri Lanka is striving to strengthen its economy through innovations and socio-economic relations. Meanwhile, Hungary is exploring educational exchanges, providing Sri Lankan students with opportunities to experience Hungary's advanced technological and scientific education systems. Specifically, Hungary offers Sri Lankan students the chance to study in fields such as biotechnology, management, applied and social sciences, and environmental science (Bryman, 2012). However, due to Sri Lanka's current economic and political crises, there have been setbacks in healthcare and infrastructure development. Nonetheless, the increasing collaboration between Sri Lanka and Hungary in the healthcare sector is significant, with Hungary's healthcare system serving as a model for improving Sri Lanka's medical services, thereby contributing to both countries' development aspirations (Klostermann, 2010). As this multifaceted relationship fosters economic and human empowerment, maintaining strong and friendly cooperation between Hungary and Sri Lanka is expected to lead to further bilateral development, educational progress, and economic growth.

Although information about the Sri Lankan community in Hungary is limited, Sri Lankans residing there leverage these connections for educational and economic advancement. While Sri Lanka does not have an embassy in Hungary, a Consulate General operates in Budapest, and Hungary maintains a Consulate General in Colombo (embassypages.com). Although specific details about Sri Lankans living in Hungary are not systematically recorded, diplomatic relations between the two countries have been maintained since 1956 (Sri Lankan Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2021). Over nearly 70 years, bilateral agreements, cultural exchanges, and diplomatic relations have broadened the scope of political, economic, cultural, and educational ties (Sri Lankan Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2021). Politically, as a result of these strengthened relations, Hungary operates an honorary consulate in Colombo (Sri Lankan Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2021).

In recent years, there has been a noticeable increase in Sri Lankans moving to Hungary, primarily for educational purposes. The growth of this community has been significantly influenced by the recently launched Stipendium Hungaricum Scholarship Program, which provides Sri Lankan students with access to higher education opportunities in Hungary (Tempus Public Foundation, 2022). Even in times of environmental crisis in Sri Lanka, Hungary has extended its support, highlighting the positive nature of their relationship. Notably, following the 2004 tsunami in Sri Lanka, Hungary provided humanitarian aid for post-disaster rehabilitation (United Nations Development Programme [UNDP], 2005). Given the strong ties between the two nations, Hungary now serves as a bridge for Sri Lankans to pursue their dreams and aspirations, making these relations even more significant.

CHAPTER 2 : LITERATURE REVIEW

In this chapter, I am going to review the main challenges and tasks that the foundation, the start-up, and the successful operation of a small starting enterprise must face, plan, and then implement. I am going to start with the clarification of the phenomenon of small enterprises. This chapter explores the definitions of small and medium-sized enterprises, their economic importance, the challenges they face, and the policies implemented to support their growth.

2.1 What is an SME? (Small and medium-sized companies/enterprises)

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are a group of entrepreneurs that play a crucial role in global economic development. These small and medium-sized enterprises create jobs, innovate, and make a significant contribution to economic resilience. (European Commission, 2023). According to a study by the European Commission (2023), approximately 99% of all businesses in the European Union (EU) are Small and Medium-sized Enterprises. Moreover, these small and medium-sized enterprises have been able to create jobs for over 85 million people. Since it has a very positive impact on the economy, these enterprises have been introduced by the European Commission as the backbone of national economies. Moreover, the European Commission has revealed that these small and medium-sized enterprises hold the key to driving the economic productivity and regional development of the state.

According to the European Commission Recommendation of 2003/361/EC, small and medium-sized enterprises are classified into three main categories such as Microenterprises, Small enterprises, and Medium-sized enterprises based on their number of employees, annual turnover and balance sheet total. (European Commission, 2023)

• **Microenterprises:**

This category includes enterprises that employ fewer than 10 employees and whose annual turnover or balance sheet total does not exceed 2 million euros.

• **Small enterprises:**

Entrepreneurs in this category are those groups of entrepreneurs whose annual turnover or balance sheet total does not exceed 10 million euros, employing fewer than 50 employees.

- **Medium-sized enterprises:**

Enterprises in this category are those that employ fewer than 250 employees and have an annual turnover not exceeding 50 million euros. The balance sheet total of the service sector should not exceed 43 million euros.

These classifications are used to develop small and medium-sized enterprises and develop financial policies. Further analysing who are Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), a 2018 study by Rathilall and Singh revealed that Small and medium-sized enterprises, which are the backbone of economies around the world, have the potential to make a significant contribution to jobs, innovation and economic growth. Moreover, according to their study, SMEs account for more than 50% of employment and GDP in many countries. When expressed as a percentage, some developed countries report a contribution exceeding 95%, according to Rathilall and Singh. In a comprehensive examination of the relationship between SMEs and economic growth, a study by Ferreira et al. in 2023 stands out. According to Ferreira et al.'s analysis, the importance of SMEs has increased since the beginning of 2007. They have revealed that this growth has now spread to the entire economy. They believe that small and medium-sized enterprises have been able to create a huge economic development in a short period.

Small and medium-sized enterprises create economic significance, increasing job creation, economic diversification, and driving many innovations. Audretsch et al. (2021). According to Audretsch et al., SMEs contribute to nearly 60% of total employment in advanced economies and play an important role in nurturing entrepreneurial ecosystems. Moreover, Acs & Audretsch stated in 2018 that emerging markets are being driven by small and medium-sized enterprises, where they drive industrialization and the economy. The European Parliament (2023) has made a major revelation about these small and medium-sized enterprises. Accordingly, it was revealed that these businesses can generate two-thirds of private sector jobs and strongly contribute to economic stability. The European Parliament (2023) also revealed that these innovative SMEs often take the lead in technological advancements and niche market development. Research by Baumol (2019) suggests that SMEs are a fast medium, demonstrating greater agility in responding to market changes and playing a critical role in driving economic competitiveness.

In 2019, Hu et al. revealed that SMEs are adopters of lean practices in the manufacturing context. Their study reveals that, while "small and medium-sized enterprises," or lean manufacturing, are gaining global acceptance, SMEs, and especially in less developed countries, face significant challenges in establishing and successfully implementing them. Therefore, Hu et al. believe that SMEs are economic segments that do not develop equally in every country and every region. In examining sustainability in small and medium-sized enterprises, the study conducted by Mukhoryanova et al (2021) is noteworthy. Their study analyzed that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are particularly important for businesses established in a globalized and digitalized landscape. Moreover, they revealed that sustainability should also be incorporated into small and medium-sized business models and that integrating technology is also very important.

2.2 Challenges / Limitations faced by SME

While small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) contribute to economic development, they face many challenges and constraints that hinder their growth, sustainability, and competitiveness. Among them, financial constraints, regulatory burdens, weaknesses in technological implementation, and major obstacles to market competition are prominent. The following are some of the basic constraints that have been studied and identified by various researchers. Among them, they can be categorized as Financial Constraints, Technological Barriers, Regulatory and Compliance Issues, Market Competition and Globalization, Skilled Workforce Shortages, Limited Access to International Markets, and Innovation Constraints.

Limited access to finance

A major obstacle facing small and medium-sized enterprises is the fact that they face various barriers from production to marketing. According to Beck and Demirgüç-Kunt (2006), SMEs often struggle to obtain credit due to the lack of collateral and the perceived high-risk nature of financial institutions refusing to provide loans. A study conducted by the European Central Bank (2023) revealed that "nearly 30% of small and medium-sized businesses face difficulties in obtaining external financing". In addition, a study by Berger & Udell (2006) found that SMEs often have limited financial literacy, making it difficult to manage cash flow and secure funding.

Regulatory and Administrative Burdens and Market Competition

A 2022 study by the OECD found that SMEs face regulatory and administrative burdens. Accordingly, it has been identified that having to comply with laws and regulations imposed by governments or financial regulators increases operational costs and also limits expansion. Small and medium-sized businesses often face a complex regulatory environment, taxation issues, labour law issues, environmental regulations, and bureaucratic problems. Financial and human resources must be provided in sufficient quantities to comply with these regulations and continue to operate. However, Ayyagari, Demirgüç-Kunt, & Maksimovic (2011) revealed that many small and medium-sized enterprises cannot do so. The panel also noted that small and medium-sized businesses face difficulties in planning long-term strategies due to uncertainties such as unusual and frequent policy changes.

Technological Barriers

To develop a business, it must be combined with new technology. Digital transformation plays a crucial role in business development, along with current technology. However, a 2021 study by Lokuge & Duan shows that SMEs often lack the resources and expertise to adopt advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, and automation. In 2021, Mukhoryanova et al. stated that many small and medium-sized enterprises lack the infrastructure to protect their digital assets due to these limited technological capabilities and the risk of cybersecurity threats. Hessels and Parker Wilson (2013) found that small and medium-sized enterprises also face problems when dealing with multinational companies, and that due to their limited economies of scale, they have to compete on production, pricing, innovation, and market access.

As mentioned above, small and medium-sized entrepreneurs have to face various types of problems, and therefore they are always facing tough struggles in their entrepreneurship.

2.3 Opportunities for SME

Cressy and Olofsson's seminal work, "A Comprehensive Analysis of the Financial Environment for European Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises," published in 1997, provided a long-term perspective on SMEs. This study mainly addresses the challenges faced by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in securing financing and highlights how they can overcome them and improve their opportunities. They have analyzed four ways in which small

and medium-sized enterprises can develop their opportunities while avoiding the problems faced by them. These include the ability to build diverse financing options, the ability to develop strong relationships with financial institutions, benefit from government policies and support programs, and financial innovation.

Ability to build diverse financing options

According to Cressy and Olofsson, diverse financing options mean that SMEs have access to a variety of financing sources and methods beyond traditional bank loans, including trade credit, venture capital, and leasing methods. Accordingly, they believe that the ability to diversify financing methods allows SMEs to reduce their dependence on a single source and improve their financial resilience. They point out that this opportunity has arisen for small and medium-sized entrepreneurs, as large-scale entrepreneurs are unable to do so due to their policies and long-standing regulations.

Ability to develop strong relationships with financial institutions

"Relationship banking" refers to the development of strong relationships with banks and finance cooperatives. They argue that such relationships can lead to more favorable credit terms and increased access to credit, enabling for-profit entrepreneurs to develop economic strengths that will help them succeed more easily.

Benefiting from government policies and support programs

According to Cressy and Olofsson, government policy initiatives and support programs are reported to be supportive of SME. Accordingly, the government periodically conducts policies and support programs aimed at improving access to finance for small and medium-sized enterprises. They reveal that a more favorable operating environment can be created for these entrepreneurs. They believe that they can obtain facilities such as loan guarantees, subsidies, and short-term financing.

Financial innovation.

Financial innovation provides opportunities for small and medium-sized enterprises to access new forms of financing through financial instruments and services. According to Cressy and Olofsson, financial innovation is the ability of SMEs to use financing methods that do not necessarily meet traditional lending criteria, such as crowdfunding, alternative funding sources, and borrowing from peers.

Effective networking ability

Small and medium-sized enterprises always expect rapid development and expect that effective networking is necessary for business growth. Effective networking is essential for firms to gain market access and resources. O'Donnell (at 2004, found that effective networking is necessary for SMEs to innovate, exchange knowledge, and share resources. Street & Cameron stated that networking enables SMEs to create partnerships, thereby renewing relationships, maximizing external resources and capabilities, sharing knowledge on existing relationships, and accessing new markets by participating in collaborative ventures in 2007. Ngoc & Nguyen (2009) also found that networking facilitates knowledge transfer for small and medium-sized enterprises. Moreover, Ngoc & Nguyen reveal that these partnerships allow SMEs to keep up with technological advancements, industry trends, and regulatory changes, and adapt to dynamic market conditions. However, to overcome the knowledge, resourcefulness, and uncertainties that SMEs possess, there must be not only networking support but also planned and proactive networking strategies that are aligned with the goal. Moreover, the effectiveness of networking depends on the strategic approach adopted by SMEs. Gilmore, Carson, and Rocks (2006).

Effective management abilities

Ghiselli and Siegel in 1972 studied the success of tall and flat management of organizations. From their study, they revealed that small and medium-sized businesses with a flat organizational structure achieved greater success. They reveal that the reason for this is that SMEs have fewer managers and fewer employees, which allows them to respond quickly to market changes, improved communication, and more direct access to leadership for employees. There are unique capabilities, including efficient communication, rapid decision-making, and greater employee autonomy. According to Ghiselli and Siegel, the fewer layers of management that exist in these small businesses allow for cost savings compared to those found in larger organizations. Because everyone knows each other well, challenges can be easily identified and responded to collaboratively. It has been indicated that rapid development can be expected by increasing efficiency and flexibility. In 2005, Henricks, M., in discussing the advantages and challenges of flat organizational structures, stated that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) communicate more rapidly. Henricks revealed that small and medium-sized enterprises can benefit more by flexibly responding to new market changes, being able to act quickly without delays, and being able to quickly identify and respond to market opportunities, due to the interdependence and flexibility of SMEs.

Walker (2018) highlighted those fewer managers enable SMEs to reduce overhead costs and streamline operations. Ostroff (1999) explores how small and medium-sized businesses operate more efficiently due to the smaller number of employees and management, and those employees can communicate directly with decision-makers. As they can make good and direct connections with their clients, they can create partnerships, effective communication, faster decision-making, and greater employee autonomy. Moreover, the above studies show that rapid development can be expected from small and medium-scale entrepreneurs due to their ability to make quick decisions and remain agile in competitive markets.

2.4 Why are the SME so important? – Their role in societies

Research by Grasmuck, S., & Espinal, R. in 2000 revealed that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) play a crucial role in social and economic development, and in particular in fostering empowerment and social mobility. According to their study, they examined how microenterprises, a subset of small and medium-sized enterprises, contribute to women's independence and economic independence in the Dominican Republic. In discussing microenterprises, this study has revealed that women's participation is a factor that increases financial stability. Women have been able to not only challenge traditional gender roles but also assert greater control over household decision-making because of their ability to contribute to these small-scale businesses. This study reveals that economic empowerment is a means of improving individual well-being. Moreover, Grasmuck & Espinal believe that small businesses have the potential to strengthen social networks and collective resilience. They revealed in 2007, that small and medium-sized enterprises contribute to sustainable development as they can develop broad community participation, economic diversification, job creation and promotion. They have also studied the adaptability of small and medium-sized enterprises, which they believe are essential for both effectively responding to local needs, creating economic progress, and fostering social equity.

In 2022, Durst & Edvardsson's research titled Knowledge Management in SMEs revealed that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are essential for economic growth and social development. They believe that SMEs play a significant role in employment, innovation, and community stability. Accordingly, it is revealed that knowledge management (KM) should be used to improve the performance and resilience of small and medium-sized enterprises and should support the utilization of collective expertise. It is stated that small and medium-sized

enterprises play a major role in the rapidly changing business environment and are driving innovation. It further points out that, by systematically managing knowledge, those businesses can improve decision-making processes and enhance operational efficiency. According to Durst & Edvardsson, "SMEs have the potential to diversify the economy and create jobs, thus strengthening the socio-economic fabric". Therefore, Durst & Edvardsson reveal that implementing strong KM strategies is essential to fulfill their important role in creating sustainable social and economic development.

The study of Cabal. M., in 1992, on "small and medium-sized enterprises" has well analyzed the economic and social contributions made by SME. He acknowledged that SMEs promote employment, reduce poverty, build economic resilience, and lead to social and economic development. Cabal examining the importance of micro and small enterprises in the Dominican Republic, emphasized the contribution that small and medium-sized enterprises make to the local economy and community well-being. Accordingly, it is revealed that small and medium-sized enterprises create essential income-generating opportunities, help reduce economic disparities, and contribute to social stability by creating decentralized employment opportunities. The most important finding of his research was that SMEs allow people who are trying to migrate to urban centers in search of jobs to earn an income while remaining in their communities. Moreover, Cabal (1992) emphasized that small and medium-sized enterprises can respond to local market needs promptly, foster economic diversification over time, and sustain livelihoods in developing economies. The study confirms that SMEs contribute economically and to community development, and therefore need to be supported with the right approaches, from financing to training and initiatives.

2.5 Starting an enterprise - business plan

The first step in starting a successful business is to create and properly develop a comprehensive business plan. Ferreras et al. revealed in 2017 that a business plan is a blueprint for achieving the goals of an organization and its strategies. A business plan includes market analysis, financial projections that will affect the organization, and strategies needed to develop the business. Ferreras et al. believed that this collectively provides a roadmap for business growth and sustainability. Proper understanding and foresight in preparing a business plan allows for internal decision-making, identification of future challenges, development of strategies, and the feasibility, long-term success, and profitability of the proposed business (Ferreras et al., 2017).

In 2007, Kraus and Schwarz conducted a study examining the impact of pre-launch planning on the success of new small businesses. This study primarily investigated the impact of pre-start-up planning and formal business plan development on small business success. Data collection in this study was conducted according to a quantitative research design, and data were collected by conducting surveys by selecting new entrepreneurs. The primary focus of data collection was to study the performance achieved by entrepreneurs with a written business plan after starting their businesses. Kraus and Schwarz's findings revealed that entrepreneurs who engaged in extensive pre-start-up planning, that is, those who developed formal business plans, achieved greater business success compared to entrepreneurs who started businesses without such plans. Accordingly, Kraus and Schwarz reveal that systematic planning is essential in the early stages of business development. Revealing its importance, Kraus and Schwarz have confirmed in their study that business planning increases the likelihood of achieving favourable outcomes.

In his 2018 publication of "Business plan for a starting company," Efstathiou explains how using a business plan can help entrepreneurs to achieve their business goals and strategies. According to his disclosure, a business plan is a comprehensive roadmap that helps explain the steps required to start a business. Efstathiou states strategic planning must be in place before starting a business. He reveals that this enables entrepreneurs to anticipate challenges and devise effective solutions. He reveals that planning solutions can ultimately increase the chances of long-term success. Moreover, it reveals that to attract investors, which is the most important aspect of a business, and ensure financial sustainability. They must be carried out by identifying the start-up costs, projected revenues, and funding requirements of the business. In this study, Efstathiou emphasizes the importance of conducting market analysis, which he believes can help identify market gaps. Moreover, operational planning and preparing a well-structured business plan can help secure financing, provide a clear vision for the organization, and broaden investment opportunities by attracting vendors.

The book "How to Start a Small Business" was published by Mogens Thomsen in 2009, and it revealed the importance of simplicity and clarity in business planning. This book provides practical guidance for entrepreneurs who want to start a business and presents a grounded understanding of entrepreneurial challenges. Thomsen reveals that small business owners who

do not follow a formal research methodology have faced severe failures in the past. Moreover, if someone engages in strategic planning and follows structured guidelines, even a small business can be led to rapid success. Thomsen argues that even an entrepreneur with minimal prior knowledge can start and run a business with a business plan, and he reveals that the purpose of a business plan is to empower individuals to pursue entrepreneurship with confidence.

Fletcher and Bourne (2012) published an article in PLOS Computational Biology titled Ten Simple Rules for Starting a Company. This article provides practical guidance for academics transitioning into entrepreneurship. It also provides guidance on understanding the value propositions that an entrepreneur should follow, identifying commercialization barriers, and maintaining academic integrity. Fletcher and Bourne have identified ten key principles that help entrepreneurs overcome their challenges when starting a business, not just a startup. They are as follows:

Have a Clear Vision: Start with a vision for the company and its goals, and understand the broader impact it can have on the market.

Know Your Market: Conduct in-depth market research into the organization's potential customers and your products.

Get the Right People: Working with a team that complements the organizational skills, and being careful in selecting employees, advisors, and investors who bring the expertise needed to fill the gaps

Have a Business Plan: Presenting the business idea to potential investors and creating a clear, structured business plan for growth.

Secure Funding: Using various funds provided by grants, venture capital, or investors based on the company's needs.

Stay Focused on the Core Idea: Focusing on the company's core values and identifying the impacts and avoiding unnecessary advice and misdirection.

Be Prepared to Pivot: Based on new insights, develop flexibility and openness to changing directions.

Know the Business Side of Things: Gaining an understanding of marketing, sales, finance, and operations to achieve business success.

Don't Forget Ethics: Maintaining ethics and ensuring sustainability are required when starting and growing a company.

Be Prepared for Hard Work: Identifying and preparing for the decisions necessary to start and run a company.

The importance of acquiring new business skills and utilizing academic expertise for entrepreneurial success is also highlighted by Fletcher and Bourne. The authors conclude that running a company requires skills and plans, not just traditional research.

2.6 stating an enterprise – challenges

Entrepreneurs face significant challenges when starting a new business venture and when working to make their businesses successful. Business Insider has analysed that, according to 2025, "the small-scale entrepreneurs will face major problems in obtaining adequate financing when starting businesses". Business Insider, which conducted an extensive study of 50 million American businesses, has revealed that the success of a company's business promotion is practically related to its size. It was also revealed that a million dollars increases opportunities by 25 percent. Moreover, Business Insider further revealed that there are challenges in starting a business, depending on the business opportunities available to women and men, and the business opportunities available to young and old entrepreneurs.

Nowadays, more attention is paid to "entrepreneurship by graduate students" because they have a great deal of business knowledge and understanding. Petrescu and Suciu conducted an exploratory study on "Entrepreneurship in Graduate Students" in 2024. This study primarily focuses on the threats, opportunities, and cultural biases faced by small-scale intellectual entrepreneurs. This study primarily focuses on investigating the risks of a business failing, regardless of the extent to which the knowledge factor is incorporated when starting a business.

Petrescu and Suciu conducted this study using an online survey targeting students enrolled in a digital-oriented entrepreneurship course. It assessed the internal characteristics and external barriers that affect entrepreneurial intentions. The findings revealed that although students were attracted to entrepreneurship, they would be unhappy to do business if they lacked proper guidance and support in utilizing the resources. Their opportunities are also limited due to gender disparities. It has been reported that many people give up on starting a business immediately due to these challenges. Petrescu and Suciu have also studied the production of female and male entrepreneurs and their challenges. Accordingly, male and female responses

revealed that women in particular are underrepresented in leadership roles and have difficulty proving their abilities compared to their male counterparts due to societal expectations. Moreover, it has been reported that start-up entrepreneurs face great difficulties in finding investments, as financial investments are made solely based on previous qualifications and experience when starting a business. They also revealed that many startup entrepreneurs face stress and withdraw from entrepreneurship due to the strict laws, regulations, and tax burdens imposed by the government from time to time. To mitigate these challenges, Petrescu and Suciu suggest that raising awareness, improving entrepreneurship education, and creating equitable policies are necessary. They argued that it will enable startup owners to enter the business world without fear and overcome obstacles.

R.S. Kanchana, J.V. Divya, and A.A. Beegom conducted the study "Challenges Faced by New Entrepreneurs" in 2013. The study conducted an extensive literature review on the "challenges and difficulties faced by new entrepreneurs." Through this study, researchers have concluded that a new entrepreneur or business planner faces various threats from the social and financial environment. Among them, key issues such as social constraints, lack of experience, facing intense market competition, regulatory barriers, and challenges faced in managing resources have been analyzed. This study is primarily based on case studies and secondary data. It has been revealed that securing funding, identifying legal complexities, and acquiring business skills are necessary to avoid the difficulties mentioned above. Accordingly, researchers have concluded that effective financial planning and continuous skill development are of great support. Researchers recommend three basic things to do before starting a business: thorough market research, professional networking, and the ability to adapt to changing business environments. It clearly explains how new entrepreneurs can succeed in competitive business areas.

This chapter defines small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), their economic importance, the challenges they face, and the policies implemented to support their growth. In this chapter, I have defined what SME (Small and medium-sized enterprise) challenges/limitations, opportunities of SME, the importance of SMEs, and their role in societies. Moreover, I have discussed the business plan, its benefits, and challenges for starting an enterprise.

2.7 The role of entrepreneurial leadership and community networks

Under this topic, I have studied the concept of entrepreneurial leadership and the extent to which community networks support start-up entrepreneurs. In that, entrepreneurial leadership is always based on factors such as the ability to make decisions, take risks, and adapt when starting and maintaining a business. This leadership can play a crucial role in shaping the potential of an entrepreneur. If there is effective entrepreneurial leadership, it can set the right vision for one's business and inspire others to achieve the success of the business. Lichtenstein and Lyons (2001) have shown that in the success of a business, it is not only the entrepreneur's ability to formulate all the operational, financial, and marketing strategies of the business, but also the ability to develop the business environment and culture through formal training. According to Lichtenstein and Lyons (2001), entrepreneurial leaders who prioritize education and knowledge development contribute to creating a learning organization where employees and entrepreneurs can develop their capabilities. In addition to entrepreneurial leadership, community networks also provide important support in creating economic stability as an entrepreneur. Community networks include local chambers of commerce, professional groups, mentoring programs, business associations, and friends. Ucbasaran and Westhead (2009) defined these community networks as providing a variety of essential resources and support when a new entrepreneur enters a market or starts a business.

2.7.1 Entrepreneurial leadership and entrepreneurs “Ability of decision-making”

A true entrepreneur maintains strong entrepreneurial leadership by mastering business knowledge and transformational skills when starting and running a business. According to a study conducted by Hussain in 2022 has mentioned that, when making the right decisions as an entrepreneur, proper risk management enables decisions that are appropriate for the future success of the business and proper financial management. Hussain believes that entrepreneurs with good entrepreneurial leadership qualities possess theoretical knowledge and experience in entrepreneurship, as well as a proper understanding of market needs. It further reveals that it helps entrepreneurs improve their capacity for strategic planning. If entrepreneurial leadership is implemented properly, then the decision-making of the business will be very strong. When running a business, it is important to identify the target market, identify the competitors, formulate strategies to overcome them, and carry out financial development and

management while minimizing the losses of the business. This is why it is possible to recruit teams that can have a positive impact on the organization's progress (Kirkpatrick and Locke, 1991).

A study conducted by Kirkpatrick and Locke in 1991 revealed that the abilities of effective entrepreneurial leaders are unique. Accordingly, they believe that they have not only strategic knowledge, but also the ability to make predictions about industry and market trends and make the right decisions. Kirkpatrick and Locke further comment that these entrepreneurial leaders are driven by their decision-making ability to consider short-term and long-term operations and goals, characterized by a strong vision. Commenting further, they revealed that the entrepreneurs must possess strong decision-making skills when they are faced with uncertainty. According to Kirkpatrick, the entrepreneurs are able not only to assess risks, but also to overcome challenges with ease, choose the best course of action from among the strategies available to them, and conduct market research and analysis in making structured decisions due to this decision-making ability.

2.7.2 Entrepreneurial leadership and entrepreneurs “Ability of Risk Taking”

When discussing the qualities of a leader, risk-taking is a hallmark of leadership. A business seeks to achieve economically viable goals while facing constant risks and challenges. In that case, if someone has a proper entrepreneurial leadership spirit, they should not be afraid of risks but should overcome them properly. When running a business, the risk of failure can occur in several ways. They can be categorized as economic risk when making investments, risk when launching products, risk when entering new markets, and risk arising from cultural, social or political decisions.

Therefore, Zhao and Seibert (2006) revealed that entrepreneurs constantly face this risk of failure. They explained that an effective entrepreneurial leader who can manage these risks properly knows how to constantly balance risk and reward. The concept of risk-taking has an important place in entrepreneurial leadership. This is because it allows entrepreneurs to make the best decisions for the development of the organization, even though they are exposed to failures. When a business faces certain challenges, entrepreneurs acting impulsively or recklessly can cause major problems for the development of the organization. However, if

entrepreneurial leadership is in place, businesses can face uncertainties using knowledge and intelligence. Zhao and Seibert (2006)

2.7.3 Entrepreneurial leadership and entrepreneurs “Ability to adapt”

An important leadership quality for entrepreneurs is the ability to adapt. The economic, social, and cultural challenges outlined above have created a rapidly changing business environment today. In such a dynamic business society, entrepreneurs must be mature individuals who can make flexible decisions without being challenged. Leaders must have the ability to adapt, identify emerging trends or unexpected challenges in the market, and understand market shifts. Nadkarni and Herrmann (2010) revealed that this can help businesses maintain stability even when faced with disruptions in a competitive environment. The study further reveals that entrepreneurial leaders can be flexible even in a complex and dynamic environment, and by carefully studying changes in consumer behavior, they can easily find opportunities for new adaptations and be commercially successful. In this way, researchers have consistently defined that entrepreneurial leadership can lead to business development.

2.7.4 Community networks and entrepreneurs

Entrepreneurship is the process of successfully overcoming various challenges from the beginning to the end of a business, creating economic stability, and successfully confronting one's competitors to gain a competitive advantage. In this, community networks provide opportunities for entrepreneurs to move towards success. Community networks are defined as the combination of social capital, business mentorship, financial support, and cultural adaptation.

2.7.5 Social Capital and Its Impact on Entrepreneurial Success

Social capital plays a huge role in entrepreneurship and the entrepreneur. Accordingly, entrepreneurs can build a trusting business environment by connecting with their family, friends, and professional contacts. Putnam revealed in 2000 that it has a positive impact on business development. Putnam also revealed that these relationships are business assets and play a crucial role in achieving goals, making decisions, finding new business opportunities, and facing unexpected challenges. As Coleman (1988) emphasized, when social capital is strong, entrepreneurs can easily access scarce resources and develop trust and cooperation.

Aldrich and Kim (2007) also suggest that strong social networks enable businesses to identify new opportunities, operate legally, and operate with credibility when social capital is strong.

Research by Adivijaya, Adam, and Rafsanjani (2023) has revealed that the creativity and adaptability of sole proprietors are often low due to their isolation from these social networks. Community networks contribute to creating a conducive environment for entrepreneurial activity as they allow entrepreneurs to access mentorship and support systems. This social capital is defined as investors, government agencies, educational institutions, friends, business associates, and support organizations. Ramos-Rodriguez et al. (2024) highlight those social networks help entrepreneurship, from identifying new business opportunities to developing capabilities.

2.7.6 Business Mentorship and Its Impact on Entrepreneurial Success

Mentoring is essential from the start and throughout the life of a business to succeed. Mentoring is defined by Elfring and Hulsink (2003) as an area that can significantly impact the success and sustainability of new businesses, in particular. In general, when conducting a business, consultants can overcome various obstacles from beginning to end, identify complex situations, and properly prepare the legal background of the business. It provides emotional relief and the ability to be free from the pressures of entrepreneurship.

Moreover, Hulsink (2003) believes that Business Mentorship provides the ability to identify and gain knowledge to ease the complexities of business ownership, and to create opportunities to persevere in difficult times. According to Carter and Jones-Evans (2006), comparing businesses with and without mentors, it was found that entrepreneurs with mentors had a higher probability of business survival and growth. When mentors are present, they are aligned with the vision and purpose, learn how to manage teams, lead teams, and teach conflict management. Entrepreneurs who are supported by mentors, working with vision and purpose, gain the confidence to take risks and innovate, which is necessary for business growth.

2.7.7 Financial Support and its impact on entrepreneurship

Access to financial support is a fundamental component of the success of an entrepreneur. Entrepreneurs sometimes face setbacks, especially in the economic sphere. In such cases, new entrepreneurs often face challenges in obtaining funding. As Harrison and Mason (2000) point out, entrepreneurs can obtain financial support from sources such as friendly investors, venture

capitalists, and crowdfunding platforms when they face financial setbacks. One of the main problems faced by entrepreneurs when seeking financial assistance or loans is the reluctance or delay in approving loans by traditional financial institutions. However, it will be a great help to the entrepreneur as the entrepreneur can quickly and informally raise funds through their community networks, especially through groups such as family and friends. This financial support is often very beneficial to the entrepreneur, as it may be interest-free loans, loans with low interest rates, or more favorable repayment terms. Westhead, Wright, and Ucbasaran (2001).

2.7.8 Cultural Adaptation: Overcoming Barriers to Business Success

If starting a business in a foreign environment, the organizational network that is more important for such an entrepreneur is a cultural adaptation, as immigrant entrepreneurs must operate their business while adhering to the local culture. If there is a proper understanding of local customs, consumer behaviours, traditional rules, and practices that are constantly transmitted to new entrepreneurs through community networks, entrepreneurs can succeed without competition, Lindsay and Steer (2002). It has been revealed that by participating in further community networks, entrepreneurs can learn many culturally valuable things. Accordingly, Lindsay and Steer emphasize that when exposed to the local market, entrepreneurs can only build good relationships with customers if they have a proper understanding of the prevailing cultural environment and customs.

2.8 The role of Business Knowledge skills and entrepreneurs

One of the most important aspects of the success of new entrepreneurial ventures is acquiring business knowledge. An entrepreneur must possess business knowledge. Otherwise, everything from making effective decisions to running a business becomes ineffective. There are several ways to acquire business knowledge. In this study, I will focus on three main aspects: Theoretical Knowledge, Experiences, and Market Awareness.

2.8.1 Impact of Knowledge and Training on Entrepreneurial Success

It is very easy to create a future entrepreneur through theoretical knowledge because this theoretical knowledge enables one to gain only a basic understanding of entrepreneurship. Structured entrepreneurship training programs and theoretical education, are simply referred to

as classroom lessons, classroom activities, short and long discussions, workshops, theory studies, assembly discussions, presentations, and active, experiential learning. Additionally, Bae et al. (2014) found that educational methods such as internships, short-term post-graduate training, and dissertation studies can create self-efficacy and positive affect among adolescents regarding entrepreneurship.

In creating a strategic entrepreneur, it is very important to provide constant training and proper theoretical understanding. Because it is based on that understanding that we can innovate, understand what is appropriate and what is not, and understand past events and concepts to make future predictions. Research shows that it is essential to provide such extensive training to an entrepreneur, and in addition, Martin et al. believe that orientation should be developed concerning entrepreneurship education. Accordingly, the findings of Martin et al. in 2013 show that the foundation for creating an entrepreneur and improving the strategic posture of new businesses can be laid by building on theoretical knowledge and training.

2.8.2 Impact of Experience on Entrepreneurial Success

Cope revealed in 2005 that an entrepreneur is more likely to be successful if he or she starts a business after proper training than if he or she starts one based solely on theoretical knowledge. To develop the skills of an entrepreneur, there must be a proper understanding of practical experiences and the positive and negative impacts encountered. According to Cope in 2005, engaging in real-world business activities provides entrepreneurs with the opportunity to put the theoretical knowledge they have learned into practice, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and build their ability to successfully withstand risks. In 2005, Cope identified several ways in which a new entrepreneur can gain entrepreneurial experience. Among them, he believes that internships and mentoring play a major role.

This is because entrepreneurs with fresh theoretical knowledge gain a proper understanding of how to use their knowledge when undertaking internships after graduation. Entrepreneurs can learn through experiential learning through practical activities and develop practical skills essential for strong entrepreneurial success in the future. Furthermore, when starting a new business as an entrepreneur, one will be able to act with a proper understanding of the businesses he has previously undertaken and their successes and failures. Ucbasaran et al. (2010) reveal that experienced entrepreneurs often explore opportunities to improve business opportunities through networking, they are trying to predict in advance the actions to be taken

to secure financing and to gain an understanding of the profits and losses resulting from identifying market opportunities. Moreover, experienced entrepreneurs have a proper understanding of the market environment, so they can act more meticulously than newcomers. According to Ucbasaran et al, to be a successful entrepreneur even in a new business environment, an entrepreneur must possess this confidence and ability, which stems from accumulated experience.

2.8.3 Impact of Market Awareness on Entrepreneurial Success

Market awareness is the ability to act with the proper understanding of the factors prevailing in the business environment when conducting a business. Gaglio & Katz (2001) revealed that awareness of industry trends, the ability to identify customer needs, and an understanding of competitive organizational structures can help to understand social, economic, or political dynamics. Entrepreneurs with a keen market awareness can easily face challenges in business development because they can properly identify business opportunities and threats. By properly understanding past business experiences and future business needs, they can become effective strategic businesspeople (Gaglio & Katz, 2001).

For an entrepreneur to engage in business with proper awareness, he must have proper theoretical knowledge and practical training. Moreover, by participating in entrepreneurship training programs, one can create a knowledge base that allows one to understand market dynamics well. Fayolle & Gailly (2015) revealed that those who are well-informed when conducting business are constantly curious and are alert to new dimensions, experiences, and opportunities, thereby improving business performance. Entrepreneurs must be constantly aware of not only socially unacceptable laws, political frameworks, and opportunities, new taxes, and business policies, but also of the opportunities and threats in foreign and domestic markets. Accordingly, Gaglio & Katz believe that developing market awareness can help entrepreneurs understand market realities, identify business strategies, and achieve entrepreneurial success.

2.9 Entrepreneurial Empowerment

Entrepreneurship empowerment is the creation of a passion within the entrepreneur to successfully run a business (Avolio & Bass, 2004). If entrepreneurs want to manage their businesses properly, they must naturally possess good skills. By developing these skills and

providing the resources and confidence needed to engage in entrepreneurship, entrepreneurs can positively develop their businesses. Entrepreneurship empowerment provides proper guidance and support for this. This study examines the extent to which Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks empower an entrepreneur. It discusses the impact of Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks on Enhancing Business Performance and Growth, Innovation, and Competitive Advantage.

2.9.1 Enhanced Business Performance and Growth

Davidsson et al. (2010) revealed that an empowered entrepreneur is more likely to achieve greater market share, generate more revenue, and grow the business to outperform competitors. Entrepreneurs face many challenges when starting or running a business. Their entrepreneurial leadership and social network support are crucial to overcoming those challenges. According to a 2016 study by Kuratko, entrepreneurial leadership has been shown to benefit entrepreneurs through social network collaboration, such as knowledge, decision-making ability, financial support, adaptability, and use of knowledge and resources. Moreover, Kuratko believes that it will enable entrepreneurs to make strategic decisions that will increase profitability and efficiency.

These empowered entrepreneurs demonstrate high adaptability, as they clearly understand the new laws and regulations that are being imposed based on the current social, economic, and political context. Avolio & Bass revealed in 2004 that this ability to adapt creates an environment in which they can thrive even in changing market conditions. Accordingly, no matter what obstacles come, empowered entrepreneurs consistently work to develop market opportunities and develop their businesses using their strategic management (Shane & Venkataraman, 2000).

2.9.2 Innovation and Competitive Advantage

Empowered entrepreneurs are more likely to engage in innovation, as they can operate with proper leadership and social support. Innovation is about creating opportunities to outperform competitors by creating new business opportunities. An entrepreneur who, through traditional entrepreneurship, understands existing social conditions, thinks creatively, and can create new products or services has a significant impact on the development of the economy. Providing such entrepreneurs with knowledge, resources, and support can empower entrepreneurship and create a conducive environment for innovation (Teece,2010). Under entrepreneurial leadership,

an entrepreneur capable of making decisions, not afraid to take risks, and able to adapt to change is naturally motivated to innovate.

Moreover, Autio et al. (2014) revealed that entrepreneurs, empowered by social influence, business mentoring, financial support, and cultural adaptations, use education and new technologies to create innovative solutions that meet market needs. By innovating, businesses enable entrepreneurs to outperform competitors and capture customers, thereby enabling them to capture the market (Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013). Schaltegger et al. revealed in 2016, "the innovator lays the foundation for creating a powerful entrepreneur". Therefore, innovations contribute not only to business growth but also to long-term sustainability.

2.10 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework (Roomi-Harrison, 2010) (Gupta et al, 2004) (Light & Gold, 2000) (Shane, 2003) (own edition)

This study examines the impact of entrepreneurial leadership and community networks on entrepreneurial empowerment. The nature of the relationships established in this context is illustrated in the preceding discussion. Entrepreneurial empowerment is not an independent concept; rather, it is a multifaceted construct influenced by various factors. In this study, two

key variables were selected to analyse entrepreneurial empowerment: **Enhanced Business Performance and Growth** and **Innovation, and Competitive Advantage**. The study investigates entrepreneurial empowerment based on these two dimensions.

According to a study conducted by Roomi & Harrison (2010), **Enhanced Business Performance, growth, innovation, and Competitive Advantage** are key indicators of entrepreneurial success. These factors determine an entrepreneur's ability to sustain and expand a business. If an entrepreneur can successfully achieve these aspects, they are considered to be empowered in their entrepreneurial journey. In examining the variables that influence the development of **Entrepreneurial Empowerment**, three main variables—two independent and one mediating—were identified. The first independent variable is **Entrepreneurial Leadership**, which plays a crucial role in driving business success. Effective entrepreneurial leadership involves decision-making, risk-taking, and adaptability. A study by Gupta, V., MacMillan, I. C., & Surie, G. (2004) revealed that individuals with strong entrepreneurial leadership skills are better equipped to understand market uncertainties and respond proactively.

The second independent variable in this study is **Community Network Empowerment**. Community networks play a significant role in entrepreneurial empowerment and can be categorized into several aspects, including **Social Capital, Business Mentorship, Financial Support, and Cultural Adaptation**. Putnam, R. D. (2000) emphasized the importance of social capital in entrepreneurial success. Jack (2005) highlighted that business mentorship and financial support contribute to strengthening community networks. Additionally, Light & Gold (2000) found that cultural adaptation helps immigrant entrepreneurs integrate into unfamiliar markets and navigate new business environments effectively.

Apart from the two primary independent variables—**Entrepreneurial Leadership** and **Community Networks**—this study also examines **Business Knowledge and Skills** as a mediating factor in entrepreneurial empowerment. This factor is discussed through three key dimensions: **Theoretical Knowledge, Experience, and Market Awareness**. Research by Politis, D. (2005) and Shane, S. (2003) suggests that these factors significantly contribute to entrepreneurial empowerment by equipping entrepreneurs with the necessary skills and knowledge to succeed. By categorizing and analyzing these variables, this study aims to develop a structured understanding of the factors influencing entrepreneurial empowerment.

CHAPTER 3 : METHODOLOGY

This secondary research up till now has examined how entrepreneurial leadership and community networks influence the **empowerment of entrepreneurs**. The study aimed to identify key factors that contribute to business success, particularly focusing on leadership qualities, knowledge, and the role of social support in an unfamiliar business environment. By understanding these elements, the research provides insights into both the challenges and opportunities faced by Sri Lankan entrepreneurs operating in a foreign country.

3.1 Research Problem

3.1.1 Problem Identification

After migrating to foreign countries, immigrants play a crucial role in economic development by initiating entrepreneurial activities. They contribute to market expansion and innovation by utilizing the opportunities and benefits available in those countries (Rath & Swagerman, 2016). Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary are currently facing unique challenges, including cultural adaptation, regulatory barriers, and limited access to social and financial capital. Despite these entrepreneurial obstacles, no research has yet been conducted on how entrepreneurial leadership and community networks contribute to empowering Sri Lankan migrants in business within Hungary. Due to the lack of practical studies in this field, this research aims to fill that gap by understanding how entrepreneurial leadership and community networks enhance business success.

3.1.2 Problem Justification

This study discusses the economic integration and social mobility of migrant entrepreneurs. Research indicates that entrepreneurial leadership plays a decisive role in business success. For an entrepreneur, leadership serves as a strong foundation for establishing stability in an unfamiliar environment (Welter, 2011). In addition to self-organization, community networks provide crucial support for business owners. Through these networks, entrepreneurs can gain the necessary knowledge and collaboration to overcome operational challenges and identify market opportunities (Creswell & Plano-Clark, 2018).

For Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary, linguistic and cultural barriers pose significant challenges. These obstacles impact business success, and the effectiveness of community

networks varies depending on the local socio-economic context (Klostermann, 2010). This study aims to bridge the knowledge gap by examining how entrepreneurial leadership and community network collaboration empower Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary, considering theoretical foundations

3.2 Research Question/s

1. What are the key leadership qualities that contribute to the success of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary?
2. How do community networks influence the entrepreneurial empowerment of Sri Lankan business owners in Hungary?
3. What role does business knowledge and skill development play in entrepreneurial success?
4. What challenges do Sri Lankan entrepreneurs face in Hungary, and how do they overcome them?
5. How can entrepreneurial leadership and community support structures be optimized to enhance business sustainability?

3.3 Research Objectives

3.3.1 General Objective

To examine the role of entrepreneurial leadership and community networks in empowering Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary by identifying key success factors, challenges, and strategic approaches.

3.3.2 Specific Objectives

1. To analyse the leadership qualities that contribute to entrepreneurial success among Sri Lankans in Hungary.
2. To investigate the influence of community networks on business growth and sustainability.
3. To assess the impact of business knowledge and skills on the entrepreneurial empowerment of Sri Lankan expatriates.
4. To identify the main challenges faced by Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary and the coping strategies they employ.
5. To propose policy recommendations and practical interventions to strengthen entrepreneurial support systems for Sri Lankan business owners in Hungary.

By integrating qualitative and quantitative methodologies, this research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how Sri Lankan entrepreneurs navigate Hungary's business environment, offering theoretical and practical contributions to the field of migrant entrepreneurship.

3.4 Identification of the research population

The research population consists of Sri Lankan individuals who are currently residing in Hungary. These individuals may have different reasons for moving to Hungary, such as employment, education, family reunification, or entrepreneurship. However, the focus of the study is on those who have entrepreneurial aspirations or are already involved in business activities. By studying this specific population, the research aims to understand how Sri Lankans navigate the business environment in Hungary, what challenges they face, and how leadership skills, community networks, and business knowledge contribute to their entrepreneurial success.

3.5 Selection of the sample

The sample is divided into two groups based on the data collection methods were Questionnaire Sample (98 respondents) and an Interview Sample (5 participants)

3.5.1 Questionnaire Sample (98 respondents)

Conducting quantitative research allows the researcher to collect the data needed for their study and allows for easy statistical analysis (Bryman, 2016). A questionnaire has been designed to collect information by studying Sri Lankan individuals living in Hungary under various visa conditions. This selection is not limited to business owners alone; it also includes entrepreneurs who are interested in starting a business in Hungary, current business owners who have already established and are operating businesses in Hungary, as well as professionals and employees who may have entrepreneurial aspirations in the future. In this study, Sri Lankan students and other residents who have set entrepreneurial goals, as well as others who are considering the current situation from different perspectives, were also included. The aim of including a group of 98 people was to accurately examine and reconcile various entrepreneurial experiences and perspectives within the Sri Lankan community.

3.5.2 Interview Sample (5 participants)

Qualitative research is conducted to provide a deeper understanding of the participants in the study, providing a deeper understanding of their perspectives (Densin and Lincoln, 2018). In this part of the research, the participants selected for the interviews were specifically chosen based on their experiences with entrepreneurship. Primarily, the participants were selected from two categories: Sri Lankans who have already established successful businesses in Hungary and aspiring entrepreneurs who are actively working to start their businesses. I selected these participants because they provide a deep understanding of the realities faced when starting and maintaining a business in a foreign country.

3.6 Sampling Method

The sampling method of this study was a mix of purposive sampling and convenience sampling methods. The purposive Sampling method was used to collect data from interviewees. Interviewees were carefully selected based on their experience with entrepreneurship in Hungary. This ensured that the study gathered insights from individuals who could provide relevant and meaningful information. The Convenience Sampling method was used to collect data from respondents of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to Sri Lankans living in Hungary through online platforms, social networks, and community groups. This allowed for a larger and more diverse group of respondents, capturing various perspectives on entrepreneurship.

3.6.1 Justification for the Sample Selection

Sri Lankans currently living in Hungary are justified in being chosen as the study focus due to their significant contribution to the local economy through their growing presence and entrepreneurial activities within the country. By understanding the challenges they face and the available support systems, this community gains valuable insights into how migrant entrepreneurs navigate foreign business environments. Previous research highlights the importance of migrant entrepreneurship in host economies while also identifying obstacles they encounter. Furthermore, it analyzes how social groups leverage social capital and adaptability to overcome these challenges (Rath & Swagerman, 2016).

Conducting a comparative analysis of entrepreneurial experiences helps uncover more meaningful insights. Therefore, the study adopts a mixed-method approach, incorporating both

aspiring and established entrepreneurs. The objective is not only to examine the aspirations and perspectives of those who have already achieved business success in Hungary but also to gain a deeper understanding of entrepreneurial barriers and success factors among Sri Lankans planning to start a business in the country. Welter (2011) revealed that collecting data through a mixed-method approach—encompassing both aspiring and established entrepreneurs—provides a more comprehensive understanding of the subject.

To balance qualitative depth with quantitative breadth, the study utilized a combination of surveys and interviews. This approach facilitated an extensive quantitative analysis of the trends and general characteristics of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary. Semi-structured interviews enabled an in-depth exploration of personal experiences, motivations, and strategic insights that might not be easily captured through conventional survey methods (Creswell & Plano-Clark, 2018). As a result, the additional analyses obtained from the five respondents were highly valuable. The use of a mixed-method approach allowed for a holistic understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape and the integration of various data sources (Bryman, 2012). This methodology significantly enhanced the quality and depth of the study's findings.

3.7 Data collection method

This study utilized both primary and secondary data collection methods to analyse entrepreneurial empowerment among Sri Lankan expatriates living in Hungary. The data collection process was structured using a conceptual framework incorporating two independent variables: Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Network Empowerment, with Business Knowledge and Skills as an intermediate variable, and Entrepreneurial Empowerment as the dependent variable.

3.7.1 Primary Data Collection -semi-structured interview

Five Sri Lankan respondents living in Hungary participated in semi-structured interviews. Semi-structured interviews enabled an in-depth exploration of personal experiences, motivations, and strategic insights that might not be easily captured through conventional survey methods (Creswell & Plano-Clark, 2018). The interview questions focused on various aspects of entrepreneurship, including:

- Entrepreneurial Leadership
- Community Network Empowerment
- Business Knowledge and Skills
- Entrepreneurial Empowerment
- Economic situation and business challenges in Hungary

The semi-structured nature allowed respondents to express their experiences in depth while maintaining a guided discussion on the key variables.

3.7.2 Primary Data Collection - Google Form Questionnaire

A structured questionnaire was distributed online to 98 Sri Lankan respondents in Hungary. The questionnaire contained 67 questions.

(<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1qpIQKIgwfyCaedLqW20hfTd0AoNN69hBg41SMY2Yjw/edit>)

- Descriptive Data: 8 questions
- Economic Situation: 6 questions
- Challenges and Problems: 10 questions
- Dreams, Plans, and Goals: 16 questions
- Entrepreneurial Intentions in Hungary: 4 questions
- Entrepreneurial Leadership: 5 questions
- Community Network Empowerment: 8 questions
- Business Knowledge and Skills: 6 questions
- Entrepreneurial Empowerment: 4 questions

3.7.3 Secondary Data Collection

Secondary data was collected from academic sources such as Google Scholar, research articles, and other internet sources. These sources provided theoretical foundations and supported the analysis of the collected primary data.

3.8 Data analysis

The study employs a descriptive analysis method to interpret and summarize the collected data. According to Saunders et al. in 2019, have explained that Descriptive analysis is widely and

generally used research to identify the patterns of research, trends within society, and relationships within data without making causal inferences. As well, Creswell also explained in 2018, both qualitative and quantitative data, as they allow researchers to gain a comprehensive understanding of respondents' perspectives in the quantitative phase, responses from the Google Form questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics, which helped in summarizing key findings related to entrepreneurial leadership, community networks, business knowledge, and entrepreneurial empowerment. According to Bryman (2016), frequency distributions, percentages, and mean scores are Descriptive statistical techniques and they can be utilized to present the data effectively.

Thematic analysis was applied to the semi-structured interview responses because there were qualitative data. Braun and Clarke (2006) have described “thematic analysis” from their study. According to them, thematic analysis is a method used to identify, analyse, and report patterns within qualitative data. By carefully coding and categorizing responses, the study was able to extract meaningful insights regarding the challenges, motivations, and strategies of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary. This approach ensures that the subjective experiences of respondents are systematically examined and interpreted.

Overall, the descriptive and thematic analysis methods used in this research allow for an in-depth understanding of the factors influencing Sri Lankan entrepreneurship in Hungary, while ensuring that both statistical trends and personal experiences are effectively captured.

CHAPTER 4 : DATA ANALYSIS - Semi-structured interview research

In my study, I collected primary data by interviewing five Sri Lankans living in Hungary. All five respondents have been residing in Hungary for more than a year and are working towards various entrepreneurial goals. The discussion began with a brief personal introduction by the interviewees, followed by an inquiry into their personal and entrepreneurial aspirations. The study examined their income levels in Sri Lanka compared to their earnings in Hungary, along with their entrepreneurial objectives and the steps taken to achieve them. Moreover, through this study, I explored the extent to which my entrepreneurial leadership traits and community network empowered me to become an entrepreneur.

4.1 Introduction of interviewees

My first responder was Ms. Samadhi, who is currently studying in her second year of a Leadership and Management MSc degree at the Metropolitan University of Hungary. She has already completed a postgraduate degree in Sri Lanka and has come to Hungary to pursue a second postgraduate degree. She is a woman who has seven years of experience as an administrative officer in a government institution in Sri Lanka, has also run a small-scale business in Sri Lanka, and is currently working to establish herself as an entrepreneur in Hungary. She is a 34-year-old married woman who immigrated to Hungary on a student visa. Her goal is to start a successful journey as an employee and entrepreneur after her education. Her husband, who has arrived with her in Hungary under the family reunification visa category, was also informed that he would be helping her with this aim, and they hope to build their family in Hungary. Ms. Samadhi, who earned a high income compared to the average income level in Sri Lanka, is currently earning an income by working part-time in Hungary. In addition, she informed me that since her husband also earns an income, their current income level is high compared to Sri Lanka. Accordingly, since they are already self-employed on a small scale, such as making cakes and delivering them she is pursuing the dream of becoming an entrepreneur and starting a cargo to Sri Lanka under the legal framework of Hungary after completing her studies.

My second interviewee was Mr. Dhanush, who is currently working in a restaurant in Hungary under the Family Reunification Visa category. He is married, and his wife is currently pursuing a degree in management and finance at IBS University in Hungary. Mr. Dhanush, has completed an engineering degree in Sri Lanka and has worked as the head of operations in a

private company. He is working on opening a Sri Lankan restaurant in Hungary and has already started many of the preliminary steps for that, it was informed. Mr. Dhanush who has earned a high income compared to the average income level in Sri Lanka, is already earning a significant income and expects to use all investments for his future business. Mr. Dhanush, 41 years old, has been living in Hungary for over three years on a Dependent visa. His goal is to properly start and maintain the business by utilizing his wife's theoretical knowledge and his experience and theoretical knowledge. Moreover, he was informed that for this, he was to seek the assistance of two Sri Lankan friends who have been doing business in Hungary for almost 10 years.

The next interviewee I contacted was Mr. Ronald, who was currently in Hungary to pursue an MSc, degree. He is currently studying for a postgraduate degree in Leadership and Management at the Metropolitan University of Hungary, gaining theoretical knowledge in entrepreneurship. He was a bank officer who earned an income above the median income level in Sri Lanka and had excellent knowledge of money management. Moreover, he also ran a business selling imported health equipment in Sri Lanka and is currently engaged in a small business in Hungary. Accordingly, he informed me that he was involved in a business that provides student counseling by properly preparing documents for the issuance of student visas to European countries. However, his ambition is to develop his business after receiving a proper education in entrepreneurship and becoming financially strong. Mr. Ronald, who is 30 years old, is still single and hopes to build a stable family life in Hungary one day, having chosen a Sri Lankan woman as his girlfriend.

My fourth interviewee was Mr. Sameera. He is currently 34 years old and married, and he says that he has been in Hungary for over a year now. Mr. Sameera's wife is currently studying for a degree in chemistry at a Hungarian university, while Mr. Sameera came to Hungary under the Family Reunification Visa category and is currently earning an income by starting a small business. In addition, he was informed that he earns a significant income by distributing food through WOLT. However, it was informed that Mr. Sameera, who also runs a business in Sri Lanka, has a relatively low income in Hungary compared to Sri Lanka. Although he has not studied entrepreneurship theoretically, he was informed that he has a great understanding of entrepreneurship, as he has been engaged in entrepreneurship for over 10 years. Moreover, he hopes to build his family in Hungary after establishing himself as a businessman. He is a small

entrepreneur with a big business plan, and he also explained to me the obstacles that stood in the way of reaching the peak of his entrepreneurial journey.

My last interviewee was Mr. Ronan Nanayakkara, who is 82 years old. He has served as the Honorary Consul of Hungary in Sri Lanka for over 20 years. He has close connections with the Hungarian government and many university colleagues, as well as Hungarian businesses. Moreover, Mr. Rohan Nanayakkara has obtained permanent residency in Hungary. Many of his Sri Lankan businesses are still in a better financial position, and he has also invested in several businesses in Hungary. He is the owner of Ronan Air (Established in 2014, which was envisioned as a Hungarian airline aiming to enhance travel connectivity between major European cities) and Ronan Group Kft. (Registered in Hungary in 2014 and represents 25 leading Hungarian universities, facilitating educational opportunities for international students). Mr. Rohan Nanayakkara, who has a high level of income in Sri Lanka, is also a high-income entrepreneur in Hungary. He has many positive attitudes towards Hungary, and he happily informed me that he is married and currently living a stable life in Hungary. Because of his discussion, I understood that Mr. Rohan Nanayakkara, through his ability and connections, has built a very important reputation in Hungary as well as in Sri Lanka. The specific reason for choosing Mr. Rohan Nanayakkara for my interview was that it was very important to identify the problems, challenges, and opportunities he faced as a foreigner (especially as a Sri Lankan) in succeeding as an entrepreneur in Hungary.

4.2 Expectations and plans before arrival

My second question during the interview was to ask what my interviewees' goals were as a foreigner before coming to Hungary. In addition, I was asked in this question how they hope to achieve their short-term and long-term goals after arriving in Hungary. Almost all respondents stated that they came to Hungary from Sri Lanka intending *to achieve a better life than they had in Sri Lanka*. However, it was stated that only Mr. Nanayakkara had come to Hungary for his professional purposes.

Four respondents (Ms.Ms. Samadhi, Mr. Danush, Mr. Ronald, and Mr. Sameera) indicated that they came to Hungary to earn a higher income compared to the income level in Sri Lanka and to achieve a higher level of education compared to the level of education in Sri Lanka, with the hope of success in the future due to the current economic, political and cultural problems in Sri Lanka. The first respondent in my research, Ms. Samadhi, although earning a high income in

Sri Lanka, aims to achieve a higher economic standard than Sri Lanka. Mr. Dhanush also came to Hungary with the same purpose, and Mr. Ronald also came to Hungary to achieve business success. Mr. Sameera is doing business not only in Hungary but also in Sri Lanka and has come to Hungary with his wife to become successful in Hungary. However, Mr. Rohan Nanayakkara, who visited Hungary from the United Kingdom twelve times during his studies and showed great interest in all aspects of the culture, ethics, and economy of the country called Hungary, was appointed as Honorary Consul of Hungary in Sri Lanka in 1993 and has come to serve here. Mr. Nanayakkara, who retired in 2013 from his profession and has also obtained citizenship in Hungary, has a single goal to expand his unique business success in Hungary as well as the success of existing businesses in Sri Lanka.

My first respondent, Ms. Samadhi, states that her short-term goal is to complete her MSc degree by gaining theoretical knowledge and then achieve professional success in Hungary about her degree. Since Ms. Samadhi's husband is also with her, her only long-term goal is to establish a Sri Lankan cargo company in Hungary. There is no Sri Lankan cargo company established in Hungary that imports goods from Sri Lanka to Hungary or export goods from Hungary to Sri Lanka. However, Ms. Samadhi's goal is to start a Cargo company to support Sri Lankans and business start-ups in Hungary and to achieve her business goals. Currently, she is working as a part-time employee in an import and export company and she is gathering knowledge about it. She hopes to apply the theoretical knowledge, as well as also the experience and skills that her husband possesses, to the business.

Mr. Dhanush's goal is to start short-term businesses that will lead to economic success. Mr. Dhanush is currently working in a restaurant and is currently gaining experience. In addition, his long-term goal is to establish the first Sri Lankan restaurant in Hungary with the participation of three people. Now he has already started the first documentation steps for successfully launching his business. The short-term goals of Mr. Ronald are the same as Ms. Samadhi's goal. Mr. Ronald is currently advising students and preparing documents for visas to foreign countries for Sri Lankan students. His only long-term goal is to become financially stable after completing his MSc. studies and establish his own student consulting company, in Hungary as Mr. Rohan Nanayakkara. Mr. Sameera is currently involved in food transportation activities with the WOLT company and is running a business providing motorbikes to people working for the WOLT and Foodora companies. In addition, his long-term goal is to spread

the name of Sri Lankan spices in Hungary by importing spices to Hungary and to develop as an entrepreneur.

4.3 Entrepreneurial Leadership Skills for Empowerment as an Entrepreneur

The third question in my interview was to explore the extent to which the leadership skills and knowledge they possess are used in their success as an entrepreneur or when they enter the business world as an entrepreneur. In it, I inquired about the entrepreneurs' decision-making abilities, risk-taking abilities, adaptability, practical abilities, experience, and market awareness.

Ms. Samadhi was my first responder, and she stated that she has a unique talent for decision-making skills. She stated that she was an administrative Officer in a government institution in Sri Lanka and demonstrated a knack for proper time management and the ability to make informed decisions when needed. Also, she has a Bachelor of management degree and an MSc in Development Communication and Extension degree. Now she is studying an MSc in Management and Leadership as her second MSc. According to her discussion. I understood Mrs. Ms. Samadhi has a broad knowledge of decision-making and risk-taking abilities. A business is an opportunity for economic gain that involves risk. Therefore, as Ms. Samadhi states, she is willing to take any risk in running her business. I was asked about her leadership skills and her ability to adapt to change. Now she is gaining theoretical knowledge about leadership management studies, and she was already a leader of a government department in Sri Lanka. Without any logic, she will be a good leader for his business, and she trusts her entrepreneurial leadership empowerment for her future business. Accordingly, she is already studying the Hungarian language at university and it appears that she has an aim to acquire some understanding of the Hungarian language and culture to adjust to the foreign market culture.

My second respondent, Mr. Dhanush, and the fourth respondent, Mr. Sameera, are currently running their small businesses and have come to Hungary with their wives and are living here based on the Family Reunification Visa category. I asked them to what extent their leadership skills influence the business venture. Both of them had very similar views and it was revealed that as a businessman, Dhanush also expects his wife to support him in the decision-making process. Mr. Sameera also has had a business in Sri Lanka for over 10 years and he hopes to start and develop the business in Hungary, using his business experience and knowledge.

Mr. Dhanush is currently completing the relevant legal formalities to start the restaurant with a Sri Lankan friend who has been living in Hungary for over six years. Therefore, he informed me that they are identifying the leadership skills needed to develop the business while carefully identifying the existing risks, adapting to the culture and language, etc. Moreover, Mr. Danush informs that they are working to establish the first Sri Lankan restaurant in Hungary, as they have a broad understanding of the market. His goal is to spread the Sri Lankan name in Hungary, ahead of his competitors, other Asian restaurant owners. He discussed with me with great confidence his risk management, time management, and decision-making skills, due to his experience and skills acquired as an engineer in Sri Lanka, and the leadership skills he acquired as an operations manager in the private sector. It was also announced that he would appoint two friends who are knowledgeable about the language, culture, and business environment of Hungary as business partners, as he is very concerned about language and cultural dynamics as risks in business. Mr. Sameera also stated that he already runs a small business renting out motorbikes and that he faces many risks in doing business, but that he knows to manage them all. He stated that he has a high level of understanding of the market and is currently undertaking the necessary legal paperwork to establish a suitable business to distribute Sri Lankan spices throughout Hungary in the future. Mr. Sameera holds a degree in Marine Engineering and, based on his professional experience of over 05 years and his business experience of over ten years in Sri Lanka, he can deal with emergencies, adapt, and make quick decisions.

Mr. Ronald is currently studying management and leadership, so he is gradually achieving financial success by working part-time in Hungary while balancing his small business. He has extensive experience in entrepreneurship, having successfully conducted economic activities as a banker in Sri Lanka and also running a business. I was informed that he would use his Sri Lankan business experience and professional knowledge to properly identify the risks of a business and to properly manage the decision-making opportunities of a business. He is confident that he is equipped with the right knowledge, so Mr. Ronal stated that he will use his business leadership skills to empower businesses in business development. Therefore, he informed me that they are identifying the leadership skills needed to develop the business while carefully identifying the existing risks, adapting to the business culture and language, etc.

Drawing on the knowledge, experience, skills, and understanding he gained during his time as the Sri Lankan Consul in Hungary, Mr. Rohan Nanayakkara became the chairman of Ronan Air

and Ronan Group Kft and is currently acting as the permanent representative for sending Sri Lankan students to study in Hungary. He informed me that his unique decision-making skills enabled him to provide university opportunities in Hungary for Sri Lankan students and to invest in numerous businesses as a foreigner. As a result, he said he could obtain permanent citizenship in Hungary. He is a shareholder and director of several Hungarian businesses operating in the trading, higher education, and tourism sectors, with offices in three districts of Hungary and conducting business activities. He informed me that he was able to do so because of his unique business and leadership skills. It was reported that he received his theoretical education as an engineer in the United Kingdom and that his experience and skills enabled him to become a consummate entrepreneur. It was stated that the business knowledge and skills developed through the business mentorship and experience provided by his father, Mr. Charles Nanayakkara (founder of Ceylon Carriers- a pioneering tourist company established in 1945), led to his inclination towards doing business in another country as a foreigner. It was also stated that language and culture were not a problem for Mr. Nanayakkara due to his market understanding and risk-taking ability. Mr. Nanayakkara stated that these leadership skills and business knowledge were instrumental in his entry into the business world in a foreign country as a Sri Lankan.

4.4 Empowerment of Community Networks for Sri Lankan Entrepreneurs in Hungary

My fourth question is how to study the empowerment of community networks to motivate an entrepreneur. To study "community network empowerment", I asked about several aspects like, how important community network empowerment, which is achieved through social capital, business mentorship, financial support, and cultural adaptation, is to entrepreneurship.

My first response was that Ms. Samadhi has a lot of support from her family, husband, and friends. She informed me that she can get a lot of business advice from the Sri Lankan community who are currently studying, doing business or working in Hungary. Dhanush, Ronald, Sameera, and Nanayakkara also agreed with Ms. Samadhi's idea and Mr. Nanayakkara informed me that these good social connections were largely responsible for achieving tremendous success in the business world. As Sameera Ronal and Danush have stated, although community networks provide knowledge, ideas, and theoretical support regarding entrepreneurship, they do not provide much support when it comes to obtaining financial support. However, Ms. Samadhi was happily informed that she was able to obtain financial contributions from family and friends to start the business. Also informed that Sri Lankan

friends and family members of Mr. Dhanush and Mr. Ronald are also working together to provide financial contributions to the business venture. However, Mr. Sameera believed that there was no possibility of obtaining financial support, experience, or advice from the family.

Mr. Nanayakkara's father was a huge businessman in Sri Lanka and he informed that since they had social connections even in foreign countries and had great financial stability, these social connections led to the initiation of business establishments. Mr. Danush informed that the majority of Sri Lankans who have arrived in Hungary are leaving Hungary due to instability and therefore there is no need for the remaining limited group to focus on business. However, Ms. Samadhi states that if the opportunities and capabilities exist, there is a suitable environment to succeed as a businessman in Hungary. Mr. Ronal and Mr. Sameera have already started their businesses on a small scale, and as they have informed us, the social connections they maintain with Hungarians are a huge boost to the success of their businesses. The family of Ms. Samadhi's husband, owns a business in Sri Lanka, and it was informed that he would be able to gain ideas and knowledge from his business friends. Mr. Sameera was also informed that he could seek support from many friends who were engaged in business to gain business knowledge. However, Mr. Sameera and Mr. Ronald shared the common view that good support in business cannot be expected from the limited Sri Lankan community in Hungary. Mr. Nanayakkara was informed that he received minimal support from the Sri Lankans in Hungary at that time, but received unlimited support from his family and business luminaries. Moreover, Mr. Nanayakkara highly appreciated the support he received from the Hungarians. Ronald and Dhanush have developed very close relationships with the limited Sri Lankan community currently present in Hungary, so the support and advice they received from the Hungarian Sri Lankan community in their business ventures was highly appreciated. Mr. Dhanush informed me that a good example of this is that the two business friends who support Mr. Dhanush's business are also friends who came to Hungary from Sri Lanka a few years ago.

In examining the extent to which these businessmen rely on the empowerment provided by social connections to succeed in business, I asked how they adapted to the cultures and morals of those social groups. Mr. Dhanush hopes to establish a Sri Lankan restaurant, while Mr. Sameera hopes to sell Sri Lankan goods in Hungary. They informed me that they would understand the food culture, eating patterns, and ethics of Hungarians by interacting with the Hungarian community and would seek their support for that. As Ms. Samadhi has stated when establishing a cargo company, political support from foreign relations, immigration, and

customs or related departments is expected. Therefore, she believes that building close relationships with the Hungarian community while conducting her business will empower her business objectives. Mr. Ronald was also informed that he is currently seeking advice and guidance from several lawyers in Hungary to prepare legal documents related to his business and to obtain information regarding regulations and future actions. Mr. Nanayakkara has become a citizen of Hungary based on his business success and skills and has himself invested in several businesses in Hungary. According to Mr. Nanayakkara, the driving force behind all those business ventures was good social relations.

4.5 The challenges faced by a foreigner as a businessman

My final question was an inquiry into the extent to which leadership skills and social relationships influence business and the challenges faced by foreign entrepreneurs.

My first respondent, Ms. Samadhi, was asked about the positive and negative experiences she encountered in Hungary. According to her, the Hungarian language and strict regulations make it highly challenging for foreigners to navigate life there. Mr. Dhanush mentioned that the frequently changing immigration laws and regulations create significant obstacles for foreigners trying to establish their objectives. Mr. Ronald and Mr. Sameera also shared their opinions, highlighting that the unstable nature of immigration and business-related regulations in Hungary demands immense effort from entrepreneurs. Additionally, Mr. Dhanush pointed out that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) face severe difficulties due to tax policies and regulations, often leading them to abandon their businesses. The only positive experience observed in Hungary was the country's remarkable advancements in transportation. However, since Hungarian is a highly complex language and English is used minimally, all respondents agreed that Sri Lankans find it challenging to conduct business transactions there. Mr. Ronald emphasized that starting from January 1, 2025, employment opportunities for third-world countries were significantly restricted, further exacerbating the difficulties Sri Lankans face in staying in Hungary and these challenges. However, Mr. Nanayakkara had a different perspective. He firmly stated that, in his thirty years of experience, he had never had any unpleasant encounters with Hungarians.

When I asked about their future decisions in response to these challenges, Ms. Samadhi expressed her intention to complete her education and either seek employment in Hungary or migrate to another European country. She added that if business conditions were not severely

impacted by these obstacles, she would strive to establish stability in Hungary. Mr. Dhanush also shared that if he could not achieve stability in Hungary, he would prefer to migrate to another European country. Mr. Ronald and Mr. Sameera agreed with this view, whereas Mr. Nanayakkara held a different opinion. He believed that regardless of the challenges, he possessed the necessary skills to overcome them and achieve success. He emphasized that by honing his skills, developing leadership abilities, and effectively engaging with society, business success could still be attained. Through this interview, I studied the expectations, skills, and influences of Sri Lankans hoping to establish stability as entrepreneurs in Hungary. Additionally, I gained valuable insights into the experiences of a Sri Lankan entrepreneur who had successfully set up a business there. For this study, I conducted interviews with Ms. Samadhi, Mr. Dhanush, Mr. Ronald, Mr. Sameera, and Mr. Rohan Nanayakkara. They shared their experiences regarding their initial expectations upon arriving in Hungary, their future goals, the impact of leadership skills on business, the influence of social relationships, and the challenges they faced. They shared their strategies they used to overcome the challenges.

The key revelation from these interviews was that, despite entering Hungary through entirely legal means, Sri Lankans still face hardships due to the country's laws and regulations. However, successful entrepreneurs emphasized that by effectively utilizing their skills, developing leadership abilities, and strengthening social relationships, it is still possible to establish stability as an entrepreneur in Hungary.

CHAPTER 5 : PRIMARY RESEARCH 2 – Questionnaire Survey

During my study, in addition to face-to-face interviews, data were collected using a Google Form questionnaire. A total of 98 respondents provided feedback. All respondents were Sri Lankans residing in Hungary. Initially, I collected the demographic data of the respondents. After that, I conducted an inquiry based on my conceptual framework regarding the leadership skills and social connections that empower a foreigner to start or sustain a business in Hungary.

5.1 Demographic data analysis

When analysing the demographic data, according to Figure 2, out of the 96 respondents, 52 were female, accounting for 53.6%, while 44 were male, making up 45.4%. Regarding age, the highest percentage of respondents (42.9%) were between 36-50 years old. The 24-35 age group accounted for 30.6%, while the 19-23 age group made up 13.3%. The remaining respondents (from the total of 98 responses to this question) were under 18, between 51-65, or over 66 years old, bringing the total to 13.3%. Regarding education levels, the majority of respondents (22.4%) held a bachelor's degree. MA/ MSc students currently pursuing higher education made up 17.3%, while 14.3% had already obtained an MA /MSc degree. Respondents with secondary education accounted for 21.4%, while those with Skilled labor certificates made up 13.3%.

Figure 2: Questionnaire distribution by gender/ by age/ by education (source: own edition)

According to responses and Figure 3, among the respondents, 49 individuals (50%) were students, while 40.8% were professionals. Additionally, 9.2% (9 out of 98 respondents) were entrepreneurs. Regarding marital status, 54.1% were married, 23.5% were single, and 13.3% were in a relationship but unmarried. The remaining were either divorced or widowed respondents. Regarding the duration of stay, 38.1% had been living in Hungary for 1-2 years. Additionally, 34 out of 97 respondents (35%) had stayed for 2-4 years, while 16% had lived there for less than a year, and 10.3% had been there for more than five years. When inquiring about visa categories, 49% resided in Hungary on a student visa, while 20.4% held a work visa. Another 19.4% lived under a Family Reunification Visa, 5.1% under a Business Visa, 4.1% under an EU Blue Card, and 2% were permanent residents.

Figure 3: Questionnaire distribution by profession/ family status/ years in Hungary /Visa category (source: own edition)

Based on responses to questions 30, 31, 32, and 33 of my questionnaires, the majority (28.9%) strongly disagreed with maintaining a relationship with a male or female friend in Hungary, while 19.4% also expressed disagreement. However, 39.8% strongly agreed and 23.5% agreed with settling down permanently in Hungary as a family, indicating that 63.3% hoped to establish a family life there. Among them, 53% strongly wished to live with a Sri Lankan spouse. These responses have been shown by following Figure 4.

Figure 4: Maintaining A Relationship (source: own edition)

5.2 Expectations and economic stability of respondents

Figure 5: Expectations of respondents (source: own edition)

Expectations of the responses are shown in Figure 5. The percentage of respondents who came to Hungary with the expectation of receiving a quality education was 69.4% (45.9% agreed + 23.5% strongly agreed). Furthermore, in response to the statement "I had a dream to have the opportunity to pursue a degree in another European country after completing my degree in Hungary," 37.8% agreed, while 18.4% strongly agreed. Since many Sri Lankans seek future stability after completing their education, 72.5% of respondents agreed with the statement "I had a dream to find a professional job in Hungary based on my educational background" (48% agreed + 24.5% strongly agreed). In Question 11, I inquired about the educational stability of Sri Lankans who arrived in Hungary for the aforementioned educational objectives. Accordingly, more than 50% indicated that they are at a developed educational level in response to the statement, "I feel that I am more educationally advanced than Sri Lanka. " Specifically, 38.5% Agreed, while 14.6% Strongly Agreed. These responses have been shown by following Figure 6.

Figure 6:Q11. "I had a dream to find a professional job in Hungary based on my educational background" (source: own edition)

In this study, I examined how foreigners attempt to stabilize their **living conditions in Hungary** compared to the living conditions in Sri Lanka. Accordingly, I focused on income levels. From question 19 to question 24 in my questionnaire, I inquired about the purpose of coming to Hungary as a Sri Lankan. In response to the statement "I had a dream to find a better life leaving from Sri Lanka," 43.9% of respondents strongly agreed, while 40.8% agreed, making a total of 84.7% who came to Hungary with the expectation of a better life. However,

the majority of these individuals arrived in Hungary to migrate to another European country. In response to the statement "I had a dream to have the opportunity to migrate to another European country," 54.1% agreed, while 24.5% strongly agreed.

The economic stability of Sri Lankans who arrived in Hungary with the above-mentioned objectives, as well as their current economic stability, was examined through the questionnaire. In question number 8, respondents were asked, "How would you evaluate your (and your family's) current income situation in your home country?" The responses were as follows: 45.4% indicated "We live at about the average income level of the Sri Lankan people." 25.8% responded, "We live a little bit above the average income level of the Sri Lankan people." 12.4% stated, "We live far above the average income level of the Sri Lankan people." These responses have been shown in the following Figure 7 and 8.

8. How would you evaluate your (and your family's) current income situation in your home country?
97 responses

Figure 7: Q8- Income situation in Sri Lanka (source: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1qpI-QKlgwfyCaedLqW20hfTd0AoNN69hBg41SMY2Yjw/edit>)

9. How is your income situation in Hungary compared to Sri Lanka?
98 responses

Figure 8 :Q9- Current income situation in Hungary (source: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1qpI-QKlgwfyCaedLqW20hfTd0AoNN69hBg41SMY2Yjw/edit>)

Accordingly, more than half of the Sri Lankans who moved to Hungary had a relatively stable income level in Sri Lanka. Subsequently, their income level after arriving in Hungary was examined through the question, and these responses have been shown in the following Figure 8. The question was "How is your income situation in Hungary compared to Sri Lanka?" The responses were, 27.6% felt "somewhat stronger economically than in Sri Lanka." 17.3% felt "much stronger economically than in Sri Lanka." The total of these two groups is 44.9%. 21.4% stated that their income level was "similar to Sri Lanka's economic level." 8.2% felt "much less strong economically than in Sri Lanka." 25.5% responded that they "perceive themselves as slightly less strong economically than in Sri Lanka. Accordingly, 33.7% of respondents indicated that their economic status in Hungary is lower than their income level in Sri Lanka.

5.3 Future Plans of Respondents

Figure 9 : Future Plans of Respondents (source: own edition)

In my questionnaire, questions 25 to 29 inquired about how Sri Lankans plan their further professional life after arriving in Hungary, and it has shown in Figure 9. A study was conducted under these questions regarding this matter, and what I needed for the study was to understand the future goals of Sri Lankans who came to Hungary. Accordingly, it is clear from the five

questions above that a larger number of people agreed on the goal of becoming a businessperson in Hungary.

In my study, I wanted to ask questions from 34 to 37, under “If you have a chance, would you like to be an entrepreneur in Hungary?” According to Figure 10, I have shown the responses for entrepreneurs' willingness to do business if they have an opportunity. For the statement "If I get an opportunity to start a business, I will take the necessary steps because I have theoretical knowledge of entrepreneurship," 28.9% strongly agree and 44.3% agree. Similarly, for the statement "If I get an opportunity to start a business, I will take the necessary steps because I have leadership skills in entrepreneurship," 45.9% agree. Regarding the statement "If I get an opportunity to start a business, I will take the necessary steps because I have a social community to get business advice and support," 45.4% agree, showing strong confidence in the support from social communities. For the statement "If I get an opportunity to start a business, I will take the necessary steps because I have experience in entrepreneurship," 53.1% agree and 21.4% strongly agree, reflecting their views on business experience.

Figure 10 : Willingness to be an entrepreneur in Hungary (source: own edition)

5.4 Role of Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks in Empowering Entrepreneurs

The primary objective of my study was to examine how the empowerment achieved through “Entrepreneurial Leadership” and “Community Networks” helps Sri Lankans who aspire to settle permanently in a foreign country as entrepreneurs. In addition to “Entrepreneurial Leadership” and “Community Networks,” the study also analysed the impact of “Business Knowledge and Skills” as an intermediate variable in achieving Entrepreneurial Empowerment.

Accordingly, under the conceptual framework, the study of Entrepreneurial Empowerment was conducted using a questionnaire (<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1qpl-QKIgwfyCaedLqW20hfTd0AoNN69hBg41SMY2Yjw/edit>) that included Likert-scale statements in the following manner (Table 1).

Variable	measurement	Question/s	
Entrepreneurial Leadership	Decision Making	I can make strategic business decisions confidently.	
		No matter how many potential risks come, I invest in new business ideas regardless of them	
	Risk Taking	I carefully evaluate risks and potential benefits before making strategic decisions	
	Adaptability	I can quickly adjust my business strategies in response to market changes	I embrace change and uncertainty in my business environment.
Community Networks	Social Capital	I collaborate with other entrepreneurs to strengthen my business	
	Business Mentorship	I am constantly tempted to seek business advice from groups close to my family, friends, and family.	
	Financial support	Access to financial resources within my community has positively impacted the success of my business than the traditional banking system	

	Cultural Adaptation	Understanding Hungarian business culture, norms, and languages will help me build better customer relationships.	
Business Knowledge and skills	Theoretical Knowledge	I apply business theories and strategies to improve my entrepreneurial decisions	Formal business education has helped me run my business more effectively
	Experience	My previous work and entrepreneurial experience have helped me make better business decisions	I continuously refine my business strategies based on real-world experiences
	Market awareness	I stay updated on market trends and consumer demands in Hungary.	I conduct market research by monitoring my competitors before launching new products or services.
Entrepreneurial Empowerment	Enhanced Business Performance and Growth	I feel more confident in my ability to manage and grow my business	Community support has played a crucial role in my business performance
	Innovation and Competitive Advantage	I am constantly looking for ways to improve my products or services	My ability to innovate has helped me gain a competitive edge in the market

Table 1: Questions for Conceptual Framework (*source: own edition*)

5.5 Entrepreneurial Leadership

When inquiring about Entrepreneurial Leadership, the responses to questions illustrating the leadership skill of decision-making, such as "I can make strategic business decisions confidently," and "No matter how many potential risks arise, I invest in new business ideas regardless of them." These responses have been shown in Figure 11. indicate that 76% (46.4% + 29.6%) of respondents strongly agree.

Figure 11: Entrepreneurial Leadership (source: own edition)

Regarding Risk-taking, responses to the question assessing risk-taking ability show that 84% of respondents (52% Agree + 32.7% Strongly Agree) acknowledge their willingness to take risks. When evaluating the adaptability of individuals with Entrepreneurial Leadership skills in business, I included two questions in the questionnaire: "I can quickly adjust my business strategies in response to market changes," and "I embrace change and uncertainty in my business environment." The responses reveal that 28.6% and 27.1% of respondents strongly agree, while 52% and 53.1% agree, respectively.

5.6 Community Networks Empowerment

The next independent variable in my study was Community Networks Empowerment. Accordingly, as stated in the section's figure 12 under one of the sub-sections, the impact of Community Networks on Entrepreneurial Empowerment was examined. Based on that, the

responses they provided can be analysed as follows.

Figure 12 : Community networks (source: own edition)

According to this study, the influence of Community Networks on Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in their business operations was examined. Accordingly, to assess the factor of Social Capital, I inquired about the statement: “I collaborate with other entrepreneurs to strengthen my business.” Among the respondents, 23.5% strongly agreed, while a significant 49% agreed. Furthermore, in response to the statement “I receive valuable guidance from experienced local and foreign entrepreneurs in my industry,” 50% agreed, and 25.5% strongly agreed. Similarly, the statement “I am constantly tempted to seek business advice from groups close to my family and friends” was used to examine the Business Mentorship aspect of entrepreneurs, with 55% agreeing and a significant percentage strongly agreeing.

The Financial Support available to entrepreneurs was assessed through the statement “Access to financial resources within my community has positively impacted the success of my business more than the traditional banking system.” Based on the responses, 46.9% indicated receiving moderate financial support through Community Networks, while 26.5% strongly agreed, and

21% agreed. Lastly, the impact of Community Networks on Cultural Adaptation was analyzed using the statement “Understanding Hungarian business culture, norms, and languages will help me build better customer relationships.” The responses revealed that 44% agreed and 32% strongly agreed, highlighting the positive influence of community networks on cultural adaptation.

5.7 Business Knowledge and Skills

In this study, an intermediate variable in Entrepreneurial Empowerment, which is influenced by Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks, was also examined. This variable is referred to as "Business Knowledge and Skills." It was assessed under three categories: Theoretical Knowledge, Experience, and Market Awareness, as shown in Table 2.

Variable	measurement	Question/s	
Business Knowledge and skills	Theoretical Knowledge	I apply business theories and strategies to improve my entrepreneurial decisions	Formal business education has helped me run my business more effectively
	Experience	My previous work and entrepreneurial experience have helped me make better business decisions	I continuously refine my business strategies based on real-world experiences
	Market awareness	I stay updated on market trends and consumer demands in Hungary.	I conduct market research by monitoring my competitors before launching new products or services.

Table 2: Questions for Business Knowledge and skills (source: own edition)

Regarding Theoretical Knowledge, 50% of respondents agreed with the statement "I apply business theories and strategies to improve my entrepreneurial decisions," while 52.6% agreed with the statement "Formal business education has helped me run my business more effectively." In examining how experience influences entrepreneurship, 53.6% of respondents agreed with the statement "My previous work and entrepreneurial experience have helped me make better business decisions," while 54.1% agreed with "I continuously refine my business strategies based on real-world experiences." Market awareness among entrepreneurs was assessed through the statements "I stay updated on market trends and consumer demands in Hungary" and "I conduct market research by monitoring my competitors before launching new

products or services." The responses showed that 54.1% agreed, with 29.6% strongly agreeing, to the first statement, while 48.4% agreed, with 29.5% strongly agreeing, to the second statement.

Figure 13 :Business Knowledge and skills (source: own edition)

5.8 Entrepreneurial Empowerment

The dependent variable of my study was “Entrepreneurial Empowerment”. Accordingly, the effectiveness of Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks, which were gathered above, was examined to study 'The Role of Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks in Empowering Sri Lankan Entrepreneurs in Hungary. For the study of the 'Empowerment of Sri Lankan Entrepreneurs in Hungary,' two main aspects were considered in the conceptual framework. To examine these aspects, four key questions were included in the questionnaire. These statements are as shown in Table 3.

Variable	measurement	Question/s	
Entrepreneurial Empowerment	Enhanced Business Performance and Growth	I feel more confident in my ability to manage and grow my business	Community support has played a crucial role in my business performance
	Innovation and Competitive Advantage	I am constantly looking for ways to improve my products or services	My ability to innovate has helped me gain a competitive edge in the market

Table 3: Questions for Entrepreneurial Empowerment (source: own edition)

The responses to this inquiry can be presented in Figure 14 as follows

Figure 14: Entrepreneurial Empowerment (source: own edition)

As shown in Figure 14 above, my objective was to study the extent to which Enhanced Business Performance and Growth is positively or negatively influenced by the support received through Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks for Entrepreneurial Empowerment. The first statement examined in this study was “I feel more confident in my ability to manage and grow my business.” Among the respondents, 30.6% strongly agreed, while 53.1% agreed with this statement. Similarly, 53.1% of respondents remained neutral. No respondents strongly disagreed, and only 1% disagreed. For the study on Enhanced Business Performance and

Growth, the statement “Community support has played a crucial role in my business performance” was evaluated. In response, 53.1% strongly agreed, 26% agreed, and only 21% either disagreed or remained neutral.

My objective was to study the extent to which Innovation and Competitive Advantage positively or negatively influence Entrepreneurial Empowerment. Data was gathered through the statements: "I am constantly looking for ways to improve my products or services" and "My ability to innovate has helped me gain a competitive edge in the market. “When analysing the responses, 27.6% and 25.5% of respondents strongly agreed with these statements, while 53.1% and 55.1% agreed. Additionally, 18.4% remained neutral, and 1% disagreed with both statements.

Based on these responses, the study will further analyse the expectations of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs when moving to Hungary, the goals they established after arrival, and their future aspirations. This analysis will help to properly interpret the Role of Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks in Empowering Sri Lankan Entrepreneurs in Hungary.

5.9 Challenges and Obstacles Faced in Becoming an entrepreneur

In this questionnaire, through the statements included by me from 38 to 42 and from 14 to 18, I aimed to identify the extent to which entrepreneurial empowerment occurs through Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks, as well as the challenges and obstacles faced in becoming an entrepreneur. These statements can be presented as follows in Table 4 and Figure 15.

Q.No	Statement
14	As foreigners, Hungarians give us a warm welcome in Hungary.
15	Starting a business in Hungary is expensive
16	Foreigners face constant problems due to their inability to communicate properly with Hungarians
17	I am frustrated by the rapidly changing laws in Hungary for foreigners
18	I am not fond of the natural environmental changes in Hungary
38	It is difficult for me to establish financial stability to start a business
39	I have a lot of trouble finding a suitable location for a business
40	I don't have enough language skills to deal with the locals
41	I do not have enough cultural understanding to produce products aimed at the local market
42	I find it difficult to deal with the taxes and business conditions imposed by the government

Table 4:Challenges and Obstacles Faced in Becoming an Entrepreneur (source: own edition)

Figure 15:Challenges and Obstacles Faced in Becoming an Entrepreneur (source: own edition)

When asked about the nature of acceptance a foreigner receives while staying in Hungary, more respondents disagreed than agreed with the statement, "As foreigners, Hungarians give us a warm welcome in Hungary." The percentage of disagreement was higher, with strongly disagreeing at 16.3% and disagreeing at 21.4%; total disagreeing was 37.7%.

For the statement, "Foreigners face constant problems due to their inability to communicate properly with Hungarians," 45.9% agreed, and 29.6% strongly agreed. Regarding the statement, "I don't have enough language skills to deal with the locals," 53.1% agreed, and 21.4% strongly agreed. When assessing the impact of Hungary's changing legal framework and environmental conditions on foreigners. For the statement, "I am frustrated by the rapidly changing laws in Hungary for foreigners," 46.9% agreed, and 33.3% strongly agreed. For the statement, "I am not fond of the natural environmental changes in Hungary," 50% agreed.

A study was conducted on the challenges faced by Sri Lankans when starting a business in Hungary. For the statement, "Starting a business in Hungary is expensive," 45.4% agreed, and 30.9% strongly agreed. For the statement, "I have a lot of trouble finding a suitable location for a business," 51% agreed, and 25.5% strongly agreed. Due to the significant attention required for tax policies when complying with business laws in Hungary, respondents were asked about the statement, "I find it difficult to deal with the taxes and business conditions imposed by the government," and 46.9% agreed, while 33.3% strongly agreed.

As an entrepreneur, when settling in a foreign country or starting a business, it is essential to have an understanding of the market as well as financial stability. However, entrepreneurs constantly face challenges related to these two factors. In this study, I explored entrepreneurs' responses to the statements: "I do not have enough cultural understanding to produce products aimed at the local market" and "It is difficult for me to establish financial stability to start a business." Accordingly, 53.1% of respondents agreed with the statement "I do not have enough cultural understanding to produce products aimed at the local market," while 21.4% strongly agreed. Moreover, due to this challenge, the financial instability faced by foreign entrepreneurs was also examined through the statement "It is difficult for me to establish financial stability to start a business." A total of 45.9% of respondents agreed with this statement.

CHAPTER 6 : RESEARCH FINDINGS

In this study, I examined how entrepreneurial leadership and social networks influence the empowerment of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs within the Hambantota region. To gather secondary data, I utilized publicly available online articles and research papers from Google Scholar to gain insights and understanding. For primary data collection, I employed two methods. First, I conducted interviews with five respondents, including four individuals striving to establish themselves as entrepreneurs in Hambantota and one entrepreneur who has already achieved economic stability in the region. Additionally, I gathered data from 98 respondents using a structured questionnaire. This section presents a summary and analysis of the collected data and information.

6.1 Research Findings of Semi-structured Interview

- The study population for my research consisted of Sri Lankans who had already migrated to Hungary. Among them, five individuals who were either aspiring entrepreneurs or striving for business stability in Hungary were selected for interviews. Based on the information obtained, four out of the five respondents stated that they migrated from Sri Lanka to Hungary in search of better economic opportunities and educational advancement.
- According to Rath and Swagerman (2016), many individuals migrate to other countries due to economic instability and limited career opportunities in their home countries, subsequently engaging in entrepreneurial activities. Consistent with this, four respondents indicated that they moved to Hungary with expectations of higher economic and educational development compared to Sri Lanka. However, one respondent, Mr. Rohan Nanayakkara, migrated from Sri Lanka to Hungary with the primary objective of expanding his profession and business rather than addressing financial needs. Prioritizing professional growth over economic necessity, he successfully established stability in Hungary as a foreign entrepreneur
- Next, I compared **income levels between Sri Lanka and Hungary**. As Kloosterman (2010) states, migrants often begin with low-wage jobs and gradually transition into entrepreneurship as they develop skills and gain experience. According to the interview

findings, most respondents reported earning higher incomes in Hungary than in Sri Lanka, even while working part-time or in lower-skilled jobs.

- The study also examined the role of **entrepreneurial leadership skills** in business empowerment. Various aspects of entrepreneurial leadership were explored, including decision-making skills, risk-taking ability, and adaptability. Mr. Nanayakkara, who is now a prominent investor in multiple businesses in Hungary and a business owner in Sri Lanka, has gained recognition due to his exceptional decision-making and risk-taking abilities. Similarly, Ms. Samadhi and Mr. Dhanush are currently studying management and leadership, enhancing their leadership understanding. The interviews confirmed that these entrepreneurs possess strong leadership skills. Burns (2016) emphasized that risk-taking, decision-making, and adaptability are crucial for foreign entrepreneurs to navigate new regulatory and cultural business environments successfully.
- Next, I explored the role of **community networks in entrepreneurial empowerment**. According to Putnam (2002), fostering trust and collaboration in economic activities can significantly contribute to business development. The findings revealed that Mr. Dhanush is currently receiving advisory support for launching his business, while Mr. Ronald has benefited significantly from Sri Lankan community connections. Mr. Nanayakkara has effectively leveraged both Hungarian and Sri Lankan business networks to expand his entrepreneurial ventures.
- Subsequently, I inquired about the **challenges faced by Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary**. As Kloosterman (2010) noted, migrant entrepreneurs must adapt to the institutional frameworks of their host countries, where regulatory challenges can either facilitate or hinder business success. The respondents identified business registration procedures, tax policies, consumer preferences, language barriers, and cultural adaptation as significant challenges. The limited English proficiency among Hungarian nationals has made communication difficult for Sri Lankan entrepreneurs, leading to considerable obstacles in business operations. Furthermore, frequent changes in regulatory policies and tax laws have disrupted long-term business decision-making.

- The final part of the interview focused on **future aspirations and business sustainability**. Due to regulatory restrictions, Ms. Samadhi and Mr. Dhanush expressed uncertainty about staying in Hungary. However, when discussing business sustainability, Burns (2016) emphasized that long-term business success depends on entrepreneurial leadership and market adaptability. Mr. Nanayakkara strongly asserted that, despite challenges, entrepreneurs could achieve success by effectively utilizing their leadership skills, managing risks, and fostering strong social relationships. He believed that adaptability and social networking could help entrepreneurs overcome obstacles and achieve success regardless of external challenges.

In conclusion, the findings of this study provide valuable insights into the entrepreneurial experiences of Sri Lankans in Hungary. These insights will inform future recommendations to support migrant entrepreneurship in foreign markets.

6.2 Research Findings of the Questionnaire

6.2.1 Demographics of Sri Lankan Migrants in Hungary

When migrating to another country and settling there, various socio-economic factors come into play, significantly influencing the demographic composition of migrants. According to the data from this study, out of 98 Sri Lankans residing in Hungary who responded, the majority were between the ages of 36 and 50, with a high representation of women. Castles, de Haas, & Miller (2014) also noted that middle-aged individuals migrate abroad due to professional aspirations and economic advancement opportunities.

6.2.2 Reasons for Migration to Hungary

Among the respondents, a significant proportion were students and workers, with many migrating in pursuit of job opportunities. Dustmann & Glitz (2011) identified education and employment as the primary drivers of international migration. It was revealed that 69.4% migrated for educational purposes, while 72.5% were seeking professional employment. Additionally, 84.7% moved for a better quality of life. Educational migration is particularly prominent in developing countries, with European destinations being chosen for higher education standards and postgraduate employment opportunities, as highlighted by Altbach (2013).

6.2.3 Economic Stability of Sri Lankan Migrants

Among the respondents, 44.9% indicated that Hungary is financially stronger compared to Sri Lanka, whereas 33.7% believed their economic situation in Hungary was weaker than in Sri Lanka. Migrants often face various economic challenges, but over time, they work towards achieving financial stability, as revealed by Borjas (2016).

6.2.4 Entrepreneurial Leadership and Adaptability

The study examined entrepreneurial leadership in areas such as decision-making, risk-taking, and adaptability. It was found that 69.5% of respondents wanted to start a business in Hungary. Furthermore, 76% expressed confidence in making strategic decisions, 84% were willing to take risks, and 85% valued community support and mentorship. Additionally, 83.7% considered innovation as a competitive advantage. Burns (2016) emphasized that risk-taking, adaptability, and strategic thinking play a crucial role in business success within the entrepreneurial leadership framework.

6.2.5 Community Support for Entrepreneurial Empowerment

It was found that 69.5% of respondents were interested in starting a business in Hungary, and despite limited financial support, 46.9% recognized the importance of community networks in business success. According to Kloosterman & Rath (2001), ethnic networks play a significant role in providing business mentorship for migrant entrepreneurs. Putnam (2000) also stressed that social capital is crucial for business sustainability.

6.2.6 Challenges Faced by Sri Lankan Entrepreneurs in Hungary

This study identified several challenges faced by Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary. Despite having entrepreneurial ambitions, Sri Lankan migrants encounter high business costs, location difficulties, and heavy tax burdens. Additionally, 75.5% of respondents reported language barriers, while continuous regulatory changes in the country created uncertainty. Language proficiency remains a persistent challenge for migrant entrepreneurs, significantly impacting business negotiations and legal compliance, as highlighted by Chiswick & Miller (2002).

CHAPTER 7 : CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Entrepreneurial leadership and community networks play a crucial role in empowering entrepreneurs. In this study, I have explored how effective leadership practices and strong community connections contribute to the success and sustainability of Sri Lankan entrepreneurial ventures in Hungary. In this chapter, I am going to write about the conclusion of my research findings and what further recommendations should be made according to my knowledge and findings

7.1 Conclusion

This study examines "**The Role of Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks in Empowering Sri Lankan Entrepreneurs in Hungary.**" It explores the challenges faced by Sri Lankans in Hungary in their journey to becoming entrepreneurs, including social integration, motivation, economic stability, entrepreneurial leadership, and community support. The findings indicate that the majority of Sri Lankans migrate to Hungary in pursuit of economic opportunities, educational aspirations, and improved living conditions. Additionally, most respondents were middle-aged individuals, with a significant proportion being women who sought professional growth and financial stability. Women also represented a higher share of those migrating for business and educational purposes (Casals, De Haas, & Miller, 2014).

The economic stability of Sri Lankans in Hungary varies. While 44.9% believed they had achieved economic stability after migrating, 33.7% stated that their financial situation was worse than in Sri Lanka. This suggests that future financial stability largely depends on personal economic decisions. Economic inequality remains a major financial challenge for migrants (Borjas, 2016). Moreover, Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary face several obstacles, including high business costs, language barriers, regulatory changes, and tax burdens. These challenges hinder long-term business sustainability and create uncertainty for migrants (Chiswick & Miller, 2002). Despite these difficulties, many respondents expressed entrepreneurial aspirations, with 69.5% showing interest in starting a business. They also strongly believed in the empowerment provided by **Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks.**

Entrepreneurial leadership is a crucial factor in business success. The ability to make strong decisions, take risks, and adapt to challenges plays a key role in empowering entrepreneurs. This was confirmed through the experiences of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs who exhibited these characteristics. Migrants with decision-making skills, risk-taking abilities, and adaptability have a higher chance of succeeding as entrepreneurs (Burns, 2016).

Social networks also play a significant role in business success and empowerment, as revealed by Putnam (2000). 46.9% of respondents recognized the importance of community support in entrepreneurship.

In conclusion, this study confirms that **Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks significantly empower Sri Lankans in Hungary to become entrepreneurs.** Despite financial, cultural, social, and legal barriers, this empowerment enables Sri Lankans to pursue their entrepreneurial goals. Furthermore, if they receive proper guidance and opportunities from the Hungarian state, they have the potential to make a strong contribution to the Hungarian economy as a strong entrepreneur.

7.2 Recommendations

Through this study, it was revealed that Entrepreneurial Leadership and Community Networks significantly empower Sri Lankans in Hungary to become entrepreneurs. The study also uncovered that individual aspiring to become entrepreneurs face numerous challenges. Accordingly, I have identified several recommendations based on the findings of this research.

Promoting Entrepreneurial Leadership Development

To establish stability as a foreign entrepreneur in Hungary, it would be beneficial if the Hungarian government supported entrepreneurial training programs focused on strategic decision-making and risk management before starting a business. I recommend establishing mentorship programs that connect successful Sri Lankan entrepreneurs with business owners, helping to bridge knowledge gaps. To overcome market challenges and sustain long-term business success, entrepreneurs must primarily develop adaptability in leadership.

Minimizing Entrepreneurial Barriers

Regulatory uncertainties, tax burdens, and dynamic legal frameworks create significant challenges for migrant business owners. My view is that reducing bureaucratic obstacles, providing tax incentives for new businesses, and developing supportive and flexible policies would enhance entrepreneurial success among migrant entrepreneurs. The government should consider such measures to support their business endeavours.

Improving Financial and Business Support Mechanisms

Many countries offer financial assistance and business development programs for migrant entrepreneurs. Since they contribute positively to the national economy, migrants should receive startup grants, low-interest loans, and financial literacy programs. Therefore, I believe that providing financial support and business development programs for Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Hungary is crucial for enhancing their economic stability and entrepreneurial success.

Expanding Community and Networking Support

Maintaining strong community networks can provide Sri Lankan entrepreneurs with valuable mentorship opportunities. Strengthening Sri Lankan business associations in Hungary and

creating collaboration opportunities with Hungarian business organizations would enhance strategic partnerships and networking opportunities, and community support plays a vital role in ensuring business sustainability.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Academic sources

1. Acs, Z. J., & Audretsch, D. B. (2018). *Innovation and small firms*. MIT Press.
2. Aldrich, H., & Zimmer, C. (1986). Entrepreneurship through social networks. In Sexton & Smilor (Eds.), *The Art and Science of Entrepreneurship* (pp. 3-23).
3. Altbach, P. G. (2013). *The international imperative in higher education*. Springer.
4. Audretsch, D. B., Lehmann, E. E., & Paleari, S. (2021). *The Oxford handbook of entrepreneurial finance*. Oxford University Press.
5. Balogh, A. (2019). *Hungarian national holidays and traditions*. Budapest University Press.
6. Bandara, J. (2021). *Economic development in Sri Lanka: Challenges and opportunities*. Colombo: University of Colombo Press.
7. Barrett, G., Jones, T., & McEvoy, D. (1996). Ethnic minority business: Theoretical discourse in Britain and North America. *Urban Studies*, 33(4-5), 783-809.
8. Baumol, W. J. (2019). *The microtheory of innovative entrepreneurship*. Princeton University Press.
9. Beck, T., & Demirgüç-Kunt, A. (2006). Small and medium-sized enterprises: Access to finance as a growth constraint. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 30(11), 2931-2943.
10. Borjas, G. J. (2016). *Labor Economics*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
11. Borjas, G. J. (2016). *We wanted workers: Unraveling the immigration narrative*. W. W. Norton & Company.
12. Brown, J. (2015). *Colonial Encounters in Sri Lanka: The Plantation Economy and the Legacy of British Rule*. Cambridge University Press.
13. Burns, P. (2016). *Entrepreneurship and small business*. Palgrave Macmillan.
14. Cabal, M. (1992). *Microempresas y pequeñas empresas en la República Dominicana: Resultados de una encuesta nacional*. Santo Domingo: Fondomicro.
15. Castles, S., de Haas, H., & Miller, M. J. (2014). *The age of migration: International population movements in the modern world*. Macmillan International Higher Education.
16. Chiswick, B. R., & Miller, P. W. (2002). Immigrant earnings: Language skills, linguistic concentrations, and the business cycle. *Journal of Population Economics*, 15(1), 31-57.
17. Cressy, R., & Olofsson, C. (1997). European SME financing: an overview. *Small Business Economics*, 87-96.

18. De Silva, K. M. (1981). *A History of Sri Lanka*. University of California Press.
19. Dissanayake, C. B., & Rupasinghe, M. S. (2019). Geology and mineral resources of Sri Lanka. *Journal of Earth Sciences*, 34(2), 45-62.
20. Domroes, M., & Ranatunge, E. (1993). *Climatic Atlas of Sri Lanka*. Sri Lanka: Department of Meteorology.
21. Dustmann, C., & Glitz, A. (2011). Migration and education. *Handbook of the Economics of Education*, 4, 327-439.
22. Efstathiou, N. (2018). *Business plan for a start-up company*.
23. Fernando, M., Gunaratne, K., & Jayasundara, R. (2019). Climate patterns and agriculture in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Climatology*, 39(5), 1123-1135.
24. Fernald, L. W., Solomon, G. T., & Tarabishy, A. (2005). A new paradigm: Entrepreneurial leadership. *Southern Business Review*, 30(2), 1-10.
25. Ferreras, R., Hernández, A. B., & Serradell-López, E. (2017). Entrepreneurship competencies in business plans: A systematic review. *Revista Internacional de Organizaciones*, 18, 57-72.
26. Fletcher, A. C., & Bourne, P. E. (2012). Ten simple rules for starting a company. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 8(3), e1002439.
27. Fodor, G. (2019). Religious affiliations in modern Hungary. *Central European Studies*.
28. Gál, Z. (2018). Higher education in Hungary: Trends and challenges. *Journal*, 12(3), 45-67.
29. Gamage, S. (2020). Cultural heritage and identity in Sri Lanka. *Asian Studies Review*, 44(3), 289-305.
30. Grasmuck, S., & Espinal, R. (2000). Market Success or Female Autonomy? Income, Ideology, and Empowerment among Microentrepreneurs in the Dominican Republic. *Gender and Society*, 14(2), 231–255.
31. Gunawardana, R. A. L. H. (2001). *The Ancient Irrigation Systems of Sri Lanka*. University of Peradeniya.
32. Gunsekera, S. (2023). Corruption, Governance, and Accountability in Sri Lanka: Implications for Economic Recovery. *Journal of South Asian Politics*, 18(3), 79-92.
33. Gupta, V., MacMillan, I. C., & Surie, G. (2004). Entrepreneurial leadership: Developing a cross-cultural construct. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 19(2), 241-260.
34. Hajdú, P. (2015). The origins and structure of the Hungarian language. ***Hungarian Journal of Education***, 15(2), 67-81.

35. Hall, R. E. (2003). *Starting a Small Business*. Infinity Publishing.
36. Jack, S. L. (2005). The role, use and activation of strong and weak network ties: A qualitative analysis. *Journal of Management Studies*, 42(6), 1233-1259.
37. Jayaratne, P. (2012). Post-war Sri Lanka: Challenges to National Unity and Peace. *Journal of Peace and Conflict Studies*, 7(2), 57-79.
38. Juhász, Á. (2017). The Úrkút manganese ore formation: Jurassic mineralization in Hungary. *Geological Journal*, 52(4), 678-693.
39. Kahanec, M., & Zimmermann, K. F. (2011). High-skilled immigration policy in Europe. *IZA Discussion Papers*, 5399.
40. Kanchana, R. S., Divya, J. V., & Beegom, A. A. (2013). Challenges faced by new entrepreneurs. *International Journal of Current Research and Academic Review*, 1(3), 71-78.
41. Kiss, T. (2021). Language preservation policies in Hungary. ***Social Sciences Quarterly***, 19(4), 101-118.
42. Kloosterman, R. (2010). Matching opportunities with resources: A framework for analyzing (migrant) entrepreneurship from a mixed embeddedness perspective. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 22(1), 25-45.
43. Kloosterman, R. C., & Rath, J. (2001). Immigrant entrepreneurs in advanced economies: Mixed embeddedness further explored. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 27(2), 189-201.
44. Kovács, M. (2020). Religious diversity in Hungary: Minorities and multiculturalism.
45. Light, I., & Gold, S. J. (2000). *Ethnic economies*. Academic Press.
46. Logan, J. (2014). An exploration of the challenges facing women starting business at fifty. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 6(1), 83-96.
47. Myers, N., Mittermeier, R. A., Mittermeier, C. G., da Fonseca, G. A. B., & Kent, J. (2000). Biodiversity hotspots for conservation priorities. *Nature*, 403(6772), 853-858.

Other sources:

1. Associated Press. (2025). Hungary's transformation into an 'electoral autocracy' has parallels to Trump's second term. Retrieved from <https://apnews.com/article/dfdf6299a614ec4e364be37c1132e446>
2. Britannica. (2021). Hungary: Resources and power. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/place/Hungary/Resources-and-power>

3. BTI Project. (2024). BTI 2024 Hungary Country Report. Retrieved from <https://bti-project.org/en/reports/country-report/HUN>
4. Business Insider. (2025, March 3). The secret of business success.
5. Central Intelligence Agency. (2021). The World Factbook: Sri Lanka. Retrieved from <https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/>
6. Department of Census and Statistics. (2021). Statistical Abstract of the Democratic Socialist Republic of Sri Lanka.
7. Department of Census and Statistics Sri Lanka. (2021). Sri Lanka population statistics. Retrieved from <http://www.statistics.gov.lk>
8. Durst, S., & Edvardsson, I. R. (2022). Knowledge management in SMEs: a follow-up literature review. **Journal of Knowledge Management**. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jkm-04-2022-0325>
9. European Commission. (2020). Hungary energy profile. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/energy-data>
10. European Commission. (2021). Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plan: Hungary. Retrieved from https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/cap-my-country/cap-strategic-plans/hungary_en
11. European Commission. (2023). SME definition. Retrieved from https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/smes/sme-fundamentals/sme-definition_en
12. European Commission. (2025). Economic forecast for Hungary. Retrieved from https://economy-finance.ec.europa.eu/economic-surveillance-eu-economies/hungary/economic-forecast-hungary_en
13. European Environment Agency. (2015). State of the environment in Hungary. Retrieved from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/soer/2015/countries/hungary>
14. European Parliament. (2024). Small and medium-sized enterprises. Retrieved from <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/63/small-and-medium-sized-enterprises>
15. Freedom House. (2024). Hungary: Freedom in the World 2024 Country Report. Retrieved from <https://freedomhouse.org/country/hungary/freedom-world/2024>
16. Hungarian Geological Survey. (2019). Mineral resources of Hungary. Retrieved from <https://foldtaniintezet.hu/en/resources>

17. International Monetary Fund. (2024). Hungary: Staff Concluding Statement of the 2024 Article IV Mission. Retrieved from <https://www.imf.org/en/News/Articles/2024/06/21/mcs-062124-hungary-staff-concluding-statement-of-the-2024-article-iv-mission>
18. Irrigation Department of Sri Lanka. (2020). Annual Report.
19. National Aquatic Resources Research and Development Agency. (2019). Coastal and Marine Resources of Sri Lanka.
20. OECD. (2022). Hungary's green transition and circular economy. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd.org/environment/hungary>
21. Reuters. (2025). Hungary opposition leader vows to boost the economy and tackle cost-of-living crisis. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/hungary-opposition-leader-vows-boost-economy-tackle-cost-of-living-crisis-2025-02-15/>
22. Reuters. (2025). Hungary ruling party to tap former rate-setter Mager as central banker -sources. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/markets/europe/hungary-ruling-party-tap-former-rate-setter-mager-central-banker-sources-2025-02-21/>
23. Survey Department of Sri Lanka. (2020). Topographical Survey of Sri Lanka.
24. United Nations Environment Programme. (2020). Water quality and sustainability in Hungary. Retrieved from <https://www.unep.org/resources/hungary-water-report>
25. Wikipedia. (2025). Tisza Party. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tisza_Party
26. World Bank. (2020). Agriculture and rural development in Hungary. Retrieved from <https://data.worldbank.org/country/hungary>
27. [Hungary–Sri Lanka relations]. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hungary%E2%80%93Sri_Lanka_relations?utm
28. [Hungary Consulate in Colombo, Sri Lanka]. Retrieved from <https://www.embassypages.com/hungary-consulate-colombo-srilanka?utm>